

3D printing of silicone and polyurethane elastomers for medical device application: A review

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ABSTRACT

Elastomers play a significant role across different fields including healthcare. They have similar mechanical properties to some of the soft tissues of the human body, which makes them useful in applications such as implants and prosthetics. However, forming elastomers for tailored-fit medical devices using 3D printing is still not yet widely utilized because of the current problems seen as innate to the elastomer properties, and the principles of 3D printing techniques. With a focus on silicone and polyurethane, this review details the state-of-the-art 3D printing techniques that are being modified over the years to allow its printability for medical applications. The paper also discusses the manufacturing challenges faced by the researchers in printing elastomers, and how these challenges are currently being addressed. This review paper shows further research direction and hopes to initiate further development of these solutions. This will allow the 3D printing of elastomers to gain widespread use in patient-specific medical devices and components with optimized functionality in the near future.

1. Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM), also known as 3D printing, is a manufacturing process where an object is formed by adding materials in succession. It has the capability of producing complex parts that traditional production processes such as machining and molding are not suitable for (Ma et al., 2019a) (Wang and Yang, 2021). This is a technology that is continuously gaining attraction in the medical field because of the rapid method of producing a patient-specific implant or wearable medical device that matches well with the human's unique anatomy (Wang and Yang, 2021). Polymers have over the years enjoyed much success in biomedical device applications. Their unique physical and chemical properties make them suitable for different 3D printing techniques and for use in medical applications such as drug delivery, orthopedics, dental, and soft and hard tissue implants. However, over the years, due to the innate properties of soft polymers, rigid polymers have found much success with different 3D printing technologies compared with elastomers despite the significantly wide application of elastomers in various engineering areas.

For biomedical applications, elastomers may be added to wearable medical devices and prosthetics to provide comfort. They are also essential for implants that need to be soft to mimic the properties of soft

tissues. In 2021, the global market has used over 2900 kilotons of medical elastomers and it is foreseen to continuously increase in demand by 6.5% compounded annual growth rate from 2022 to 2027 (Mordor Intelligence Inc, 2022). Moreover, the growth in the global market for 3D printing elastomers reached USD 151 million in 2021 and is expected to rise by 22.5% compounded annually from 2022 to 2030 reaching USD 1389 million by 2030 (Report Ocean., 2022). This market research proves the high significance of 3D printing of elastomers for medical applications in the years to come. Hence, researchers are exploring different techniques to establish functional and reliable elastomer-based AM processes.

The regulation of the use of materials used in medical devices is critical for the user's safety. These medical devices are evaluated based on the intended use, where they are used in the body, and the duration of contact, as specified in ISO 10993-1 (ISO and "EN ISO, 10993). To be considered a biocompatible medical device under this standard, it must at least pass the biological tests required for contact on intact skin, which include ISO 10993-5 for cytotoxicity and ISO 10993-10 for irritation and sensitization. Additional tests are required if the device is intended for contact with mucosal membranes, compromised surfaces, blood, or tissue. The US Food and Drug Administration issued a draft guidance titled "Select Updates for Biocompatibility of Certain Devices

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in Contact with Intact Skin” that includes a list of polymers that have been assessed to have low biocompatibility risks based on their history of use in intact skin contact applications (U.S. Food and Drug Administration, 2020), (Wyen, 2020). Silicone and polyurethane (PU) are the only elastomers found on this list. As a result, our review concentrated more on these two elastomers. Silicone and PU are indeed ideal materials for electronic-skin (e-skin) devices as they can closely replicate the characteristics of human skin. Their flexibility, stretchability, biocompatibility, and comfort make them a suitable choice for such applications (Ma et al., 2019b). Aside from skin applications, both materials have been extensively researched over the last few years for their widespread use in biomedical applications due to their biocompatibility and biostability (Visakh et al., 2013). Other elastomers that are used in medical care products are detailed in a review by Yoda (1998) and Chen et al. (2013).

The goal of this paper is to find the current bottlenecks of the 3D printing of elastomers for medical applications and lay down the foundation for the widespread use of 3D printing of elastomers, specifically silicone and PU, for medical device applications. This paper reviews the recent research trends, which include the applications and the difficulties that researchers are solving with a special focus placed on the manufacturing side. Unresolved challenges will pave the way to opening opportunities for further research and technical innovation. Research involving not biocompatible-proven elastomers and elastomer-like materials is also included in the review to demonstrate the current spectrum of state-of-the-art of 3D printing elastomers. The information and analysis presented in the paper will be highly valuable for the researchers and healthcare industries, which provide a solid ground for pushing the boundaries further for the 3D printing of medical-grade elastomeric products.

2. Elastomeric materials - silicone and polyurethane

Elastomers are viscoelastic polymers with long chains but with low cross-linking density (Sastri, 2022). The intermolecular forces between the long polymer chain strands are weak and as such they undergo high elongation when subjected to a load and recover their shape after the load is removed (Parameswaranpillai et al., 2022). Elastomers can be classified according to the type of cross-linking: physically cross-linked (also known as thermoplastic elastomers) or chemically cross-linked (also known as thermoset elastomers or simply elastomers). Chemically crosslinked elastomers such as silicone link their flexible polymer chains by covalent bonds. On the other hand, physically crosslinked elastomers specifically in the case of polyurethane are held together by dipolar forces (rigid segments). This form of thermoplastic elastomer contains two distinct microphases: glassy or crystalline hard segments that offer mechanical strength and amorphous segments that provide flexibility (Chen et al., 2013). Thermoset elastomers go through an irreversible crosslinking reaction during their production and cannot be remolded once formed (Koltzenburg et al., 2017). On the other hand, thermoplastic elastomers (TPEs) have thermally reversible cross-links, enabling them to combine the elastic properties of traditional elastomers with the processability and recyclability characteristics of thermoplastics (Visakh et al., 2013) (Koltzenburg et al., 2017). TPEs can be reformed without experiencing chemical degradation and hence are favorable for applications where reshaping or remolding are required (Visakh et al., 2013).

Elastomers can be characterized by various mechanical properties, including tensile strength, hardness, shear resistance, and toughness. The stress-strain curve provides the basis for understanding some of these properties. Fig. 1 shows the general strain behavior of different polymeric materials under tensile load. The slope of the curve in the elastic region is the Young's modulus of elasticity which describes the stiffness of the material. The slope of the curve for elastomer is the lowest indicating that it is the most flexible among the three. Brittle polymer breaks while elastically deforming. Plastic deforms elastically

Fig. 1. Stress-strain diagram of brittle, plastic, and elastomer polymers (Callister and Rethwisch, 2018).

at first, then yields and undergoes plastic deformation. Elastomer, on the other hand, demonstrates hyper-elasticity as it behaves completely elastic possessing large recoverable strains under low stress (Callister and Rethwisch, 2018). This allows elastomers to have strain-failure values as high as 5000% (Arkles et al., 2016), which means that they can stretch up to 50 times their original length before failure.

Another method of characterizing elastomer is by measuring the shore hardness value which is the material's resistance to indentation or deformation under a given load. Shore hardness is reported in the scale Shore 00, A, and D with Shore 00 the softest, and Shore D being the hardest. Most elastomers are in the Shore 00 and Shore A scale (Herzberger et al., 2019). The number in the scale is in the range from 0 to 100 (Koltzenburg et al., 2017) with the higher number indicating smaller indentation. The relationship between the hardness Shore A (s) and Young's modulus (E) was derived by Gent (1958) giving the following equation (Meththananda et al., 2009):

$$E \text{ (MPa)} = \frac{0.0981(56 + 7.66s)}{0.137505(254 - 2.54s)} \quad (1)$$

This relationship was investigated experimentally on elastomeric dental materials and found to be well-defined in the range of 30.2–62.9 in Shore A (Meththananda et al., 2009).

Silicone or polysiloxane is a synthetic elastomer composed of silica, oxygen, and organic groups which has Si–O as its backbone (Scheme 1a). The strong Si–O ionic bond makes it thermally and chemically stable (Zare et al., 2021). The methyl or organic groups on the sides are allowed to rotate towards the surface of the polymer thereby shielding the main chain. Due to this, the silicone exhibits low surface energy even if the Si–O bonds have strong intermolecular interaction (van Driel and Yazdan Mehr, 2022). The chemical structure of silicone makes it stable in oxidation, bio inert, and has anti-adhesion property (He and Li, 2020). The most widely used derivative of polysiloxane in the medical field is

Scheme 1. Schematic of silicone (a) and polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) (b) (Chen et al., 2013).

poly (dimethylsiloxane) (PDMS) (Scheme 1b) (He and Li, 2020). Typical uses of silicone in medical application includes its use as catheter, shunts, drains, dental impression molds, implants (breast, testicular, soft tissue), external prosthetics, substrate to transdermal drug delivery, and soft skin adhesive for wound and scar (Curtis and Steichen, 2020).

Thermoplastic polyurethane (TPU) is a class of elastomers that are under thermoplastic elastomers (TPE). It has the elastic property of an elastomer and the capability to be reprocessed like pure thermoplastic thus making it an environmentally friendly option. The synthesis of PU involves the chemical reaction between isocyanate and the hydroxyl group of polyols in their step growth copolymerization (Scheme 2) (Chen et al., 2013). PU is composed of linear segmented block copolymers with both hard and soft segments. The hard segment is made of diisocyanate and the soft segment is made of long flexible polyether or polyester chains (Frick and Rochman, 2004). These two segments make PU capable of having shape memory properties. The hard segment gives mechanical strength in its initial shape while the soft segment stores the energy for dissipation for it to enable it to go back to its original form upon exposure to external stimuli (Gupta et al., 2019). This makes it suitable for healthcare applications such as self-tightening sutures, sensors, and wearable electronics (Gupta et al., 2019).

3. Recent advancements in the utilization of 3D printing using silicone and PU-based elastomers for medical applications

This section details how different 3D printing technologies are used for manufacturing silicone and PU for medical devices. Other advancements pertaining to the improvement of 3D printing of these two materials in terms of multi-material printing, and porous structure even when not yet reported to be directly used as medical devices are also included since it is foreseen that this progress will eventually lead to its potential application in the medical field.

3.1. Extrusion-based 3D printing

3.1.1. Fused deposition modeling (FDM)

Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) also known as Fused Filament Fabrication (FFF) prints parts by mechanically forcing a spool of plastic filament using rollers and feeding it through a heated liquefier having a nozzle at its end. The melt goes out of it and onto a build platform one layer at a time to form a targeted print (Chua et al., 2010). Because of the constant need to melt and solidify polymers during printing, the polymers used for FDM filaments are thermoplastic (Bandyopadhyay and Bose, 2020). Hence, TPU can be printed here but not thermoset silicone.

FDM is the most affordable 3D printing process. This makes it an appealing low-cost method of making biomedical devices. Nelson et al. (2019) capitalized on this by developing a flexible microfluidic device that can be manufactured in less than 25 min and at a low cost of roughly USD 0.01 per device. In general, the flexibility of material in microfluidics enables the microchannels to be deformable thus causing control on the flow rate and pressure drop. This leads to unique functionalities such as microvalves, and micropumps. Micromixing functionality can

Scheme 2. Schematic of polyurethane formed from polyaddition process (Chen et al., 2013).

also be introduced due to the fluid-wall instability induced as the fluid flows through a flexible microchannel. Flexible microfluidics can also be used to mimic body organs allowing in-vitro analysis of cells (Fallahi et al., 2019). In Nelson et al.'s investigation, TPU was used, and with the right slicing parameters, microfluidic systems with channels as thin as 50 μm were printed. This method, however, produced rough channel walls, which may limit its application on domains relying on wall effects or precise symmetry. Valving should be achievable with TPU, however, because of its higher elastic modulus than PDMS, a more often used material in microfluidics, higher pressure is needed to actuate the valve. This makes the sealing more challenging, especially since the channel and membrane have rough printed surfaces (Nelson et al., 2019).

Printing porous structures is gaining attraction for medical applications. An example of this is done by Ma et al. (2019a) who developed a material extrusion-based 3D printing process to produce customized diabetic insoles with porous structural units using TPE filament. To lessen the symptoms of diabetic foot, a customized insole with a metatarsal dome and arch support is needed to uniformly distribute the plantar pressure. Different locations on the foot need different stiffness and so they designed different porous structural units to generate different moduli at various points of the insole. These porous structural units cannot be made using traditional methods such as molding and machining. Thus, 3D printing is a necessary process to successfully produce a foot insole for diabetic patients. The percentage of the infill pattern can also be adjusted to get the desired hardness for the orthotic insole (Yarwindran et al., 2016). Xie et al. (2021a) used additive manufacturing in producing customized bionic sports soles for the elderly whose comfort and safety are critical. This FDM 3D printing process used here was found cheap and fast in producing this high-performance bionic sole with uniform stress distribution.

Multimaterial printing can be done using FDM printer for sensor applications. NinjaTek Eel (NinjaFlex, 2018) is a commercially available TPU-based filament with conductive fillers. This was used by Georgopoulou et al. (2021) in making embedded sensors.

Dual printing using two materials, TPU and polyethylene glycol (PETG) was done by Katschnig et al. (2020) in producing FDM printed patient-specific biofunctional maxillofacial implant (Fig. 2a). The implant is comprised of TPU outer layer as the soft shell for stopping cracks, and PETG-filled core for stiffness. This combination provided enhanced mechanical performance. The introduction of TPU not only served as a crack absorber but also as bioactive shell providing bio-functionality to the implant.

Multimaterial printing is also rapidly explored for drug delivery applications. A study by Domínguez-Robles et al. (2020) used drug-loaded TPU to print vaginal meshes as soft tissue reinforcement in vaginal surgery. The levofloxacin drug was coated to the TPU pellet before it was transformed to a filament shape. The flexibility of TPU compared to polyactic acid (PLA) makes it a more suitable material for this purpose because its flexibility makes it adhere and conform to the tissue better than the rigid one (Domínguez-Robles et al., 2020). Mathew et al. (2019) also utilized multi-material printing by adding tetracycline hydrochloride (TC) drug into TPU for producing an anti-infective dialysis catheter (Fig. 2b). The drug was infused into TPU via an oil method for coating it into TPU pellets. A similar method was also used by Martin et al. (2021) to add drugs to TPU to produce drug-loaded vascular grafts. They successfully used a dual extrusion printer for producing grafts with two different drugs that cannot be formulated together because of incompatibility. The product passed cytocompatibility and hemocompatibility tests making it applicable to clinical applications.

3.1.2. Direct Ink Writing (DIW)

Direct Ink Writing (DIW) is another extrusion-based printing. It makes use of either air pressure, a piston, or a screw extruder to push the ink through the nozzle. After it is deposited into the build platform, the layer is cured either by photopolymerization or thermal curing (Zhou et al., 2020). Compared with FDM printing, the DIW can print soft

Fig. 2. Elastomeric medical devices 3D printed using FDM: a) dual printed TPU-PETG biofunctional maxillofacial implant (Katschnig et al., 2020), and b) anti-infective dialysis catheter (Mathew et al., 2019).

materials of hardness below shore 85 A (Miron et al., 2021). Bioplotter of EnvisionTEC is a commercial 3D printer that uses DIW technology to extrude two-component silicone (EnvisionTEC).

DIW can be used to bioprint cells, hydrogels, and biomolecules to generate 3D tissue models for disease research and drug testing. Joung et al. (2018) created a spinal cord tissue-like platform by printing neuronal and glial progenitor cells in a 3D printed silicone scaffold (Fig. 3a). The bioprinted brain progenitor cells showed significant axon propagation in the scaffold channels. This technique has the potential to be used for in vitro modeling of spinal cord injury as well as an implant. Because each injury is unique, 3D printing enables the creation of patient-specific solutions. Coulter et al. (2019) printed heart valve prosthesis by DIW printing on a custom-built non-planar 3D printer (Fig. 3g). The workflow provides tunable geometry and the use of biocompatible silicones with tunable properties to make it patient-specific. This can be used as a model system for in vitro disease modeling and physical simulators.

The usage of 3D printed parts for medication distribution can be essential in the pharmaceutical industry because it can be used for customization and modification of the drug to each patient's specific needs. Holländer et al. (2018) created 3D printed drug-containing structures utilizing UV-curable PDMS and heat-sensitive active pharmaceutical components. By altering the surface area/volume ratio, this drug-loaded PDMS device may release the medication at different speeds. Because the entire 3D printing process took place at room temperature, this technology proved to be a viable alternative for creating devices containing temperature-sensitive medications.

DIW can also be employed for the fabrication of flexible electronics by printing elastomers with embedded conductive material. Zhou et al. (2018) utilized DIW printing to create a wearable sensor that contained Ga-liquid metal embedded in silicone (Fig. 3e). This was accomplished by using two coaxial nozzles. The liquid metal is extruded through an inner nozzle, while the silicone is printed through an outer nozzle. This led to the development of a solenoid-type flexible multifunction inductance sensor capable of correctly measuring the curvature of a finger and the degree of bending deformation of an endoscope. Lind et al. (2017) developed instrumented cardiac microphysiological devices (Fig. 3b) via multimaterial DIW printer with multiple nozzles. Several layers were printed using different inks to create this device. The initial layer is constructed of biocompatible dextran film, which serves as a sacrificial release layer enabling easy removal of the print from the substrate. This was followed by printing dilute TPU as the base. Strain gage wire was

printed on top of it with dilute TPU ink containing carbon nanoparticles. This was then coated with diluted TPU. After that, PDMS filaments were printed to serve as guides for cardiomyocytes to build anisotropic laminar tissues. The electrical leads and contact pads were then printed with silver (Ag) particle-filled polyamide ink. This technology is adjustable and enables rapid customization of the device's geometrical, mechanical, and biochemical properties based on the needs of the patients. Valentine et al. (2017) employed multimaterial DIW printing of conductive and insulating elastomeric materials to build high-performance soft electronics (Fig. 3d) for strain and pressure sensing. The inks were composed of TPU for the insulating matrix and Ag with TPU for the conductive trace. The 3D printing process was combined with an automated pick-and-place for attaching the electrical components. The interconnections between the 3D-printed conductive electrodes and electrical components were made by printing the conductive traces. This method allows surface-mount electrical components of any shape and size to be easily incorporated onto printed soft wearable circuitry. Other studies for 3D printing of biomedical sensing devices can be found in a review made by Ali et al. (2022).

3.1.3. Freeform reverse embedding (FRE)

Freeform reverse embedding (FRE) is a type of DIW that permits the printing of low viscosity inks that would otherwise be difficult to print with a typical DIW setup (Zhou et al., 2020). In this type of 3D printing, the ink is extruded into a support matrix (Chen et al., 2020). It is also another way of printing low elastic modulus elastomer that needs support for overhanging features.

Different ways of printing can be explored by using different combinations of the support and extruded ink material. In a study by Hinton et al. (2016), hydrophobic PDMS ink was injected into a hydrophilic support. The hydrophobic and hydrophilic property makes the ink and support immiscible to each other. The same printing process was used by Abdollahi et al. (2020) in printing patient-specific wearable silicone cuffs for pulse oximeter (Fig. 3i). Muth et al. (2014) employed FRE by printing a conductive carbon grease ink into an uncured silicone reservoir to make stretchable sensors Fig. 3f. The sensors were exhibiting good electrical performance until 400% strain. O'Bryan et al. (2017) created a self-healing microgel support material that allows the nozzle to continually traverse the same location during printing while also supporting the printed structures. This enabled the printing of silicone structures such as model trachea implants and silicone scaffolds with sinusoidal wave patterns (Fig. 3c). Alioglu et al. (2023) developed a

Fig. 3. Elastomeric biomedical devices 3D printed using DIW and FRE printing: a) DIW-printed spinal cord tissue-like platform (Joung et al., 2018), b) DIW-printed embedded sensor for instrumented cardiac microphysiological devices made from silicone and carbon nanotubes (Lind et al., 2017), c) FRE-printed model trachea implant and sinusoidal wave-patterned scaffold (O'Bryan et al., 2017), d) DIW-printed embedded sensor made of TPU with Ag (Valentine et al., 2017), e) DIW coaxial printing of embedded sensor from silicone and liquid metal (Zhou et al., 2018), f) FRE-printed embedded sensor from carbon ink on silicone (Muth et al., 2014), g) DIW-printed heart valve prosthesis printed on a non-planar build platform (Coulter et al., 2019), h) FRE-printed microfluidic devices using water-soluble sacrificial ink printed in a silicone composite bath (Alioglu et al., 2023), i) FRE-printed pulse oximeter (Abdollahi et al., 2020).

silicone composite that serves as a functional support bath to a sacrificial ink that is ejected from the 3D printer nozzle. The sacrificial ink by flushing water through the channels. Using this method, complex-shaped microfluidic devices were made (Fig. 3h). Duraivel et al. (2023) formulated a support material using a silicone oil emulsion. This unique support material demonstrates minimal interfacial tension when in contact with silicone-based inks, effectively eliminating the disruptive forces that typically cause deformation and breakage of printed silicone features. As a result, it becomes possible to successfully print silicone with intricate structures and features as small as 8 μm in

diameter.

One commercially available printer that uses FRE technology is PICSIMA (Fripp Design Limited, 2017). In here, the support matrix is composed of silicone base polymer, crosslinker, and thickener. The ink composed of a curing agent is injected into the support matrix. Curing only occurs at the locations where the curing agent is deposited. With this printer, there is no need to specially formulate the inks. The commercially available 2-component medical grade silicone can be used.

3.1.4. Material jetting

Material jetting, commonly known as ink jetting, relies on the controlled release of droplets of melted materials (ink) to form layer by layer 3D printed object. It selectively deposits ink out of a nozzle or multiple nozzles into a build platform. Once, the material is deposited, it is cured by UV light or heat (Bandyopadhyay and Bose, 2020) to form a solid object. This type of printer is suitable for a wide range of polymer materials in the thermoplastic, thermosetting, and elastomer group. There are two types of material jetting 3D printers, Continuous Inkjet (CIJ) printing and Drop-On-Demand (DOD) printing. CIJ emits the fluid ink continuously. The ink that is deposited into the building platform is done by deflector plates that are charged or uncharged to deflect the ink droplet when it is not needed. The DOD, on the other hand, just releases droplets of ink when necessary (Zhou et al., 2020).

Material jetting using PolyJet printer by Stratasys was used by Hassani et al. (2017) to produce an implantable device to contract the bladder for people suffering from underactive bladder or detrusor underactivity (DU). The device is composed of a vest that is 3D printed using flexible rubber-like material TangoPlusBlack by PolyJet (Fig. 4b). This was coupled with a shape memory alloy that serves as the actuator to contract the bladder. This device was successfully implanted and tested on an anesthetized rat.

DOD printer by ACEO Wacker was used in a clinical study by Unkovskiy et al. (2018) in directly 3D printing a silicone facial

prosthesis (Fig. 4a). Pure silicone without any solvent is used in this study. The silicone is cured using platinum-catalyzed polymerization. The 3D printed part using this technology suffers from low resolution, hence there is a need for additional finishing steps. To remove the staircase effect due to printing, additional processes involving fine milling and sealing with silicone coating were done. Sealant with color was utilized to create a more realistic color match.

With DOD technology, multi-material 3D printing can be achieved using multiple jetting heads. It can be used in soft robotic grippers that need several materials with different stiffness in creating the micro-structured jamming/sensing layer (Xie et al., 2021b). Unkovskiy et al. (2021b) utilized the multi-material capability of DOD in printing auricular prostheses (Fig. 4d). The printed prosthesis is made of three different shore hardness in different locations. The concha, lobe and bulk part for retention is made of 40 A, 20 A, and 60 A shore hardness respectively. This multi-material printing provides an excellent prosthesis fit with the patient's anatomy, resulting in patient's comfort. However, the resulting aesthetic appearance was judged as inferior to the conventional processing. The skin structure was not possible to be incorporated to the prosthesis because of the poor printer resolution. Multicolor printing in the medical grade silicone was also not found feasible.

Unkovskiy et al. (2021a) also used the multimaterial capability of DOD to print customized multilayer sports mouthguards (Fig. 4c). They

Fig. 4. Elastomeric medical devices 3D printed using material jetting: a) nasal prosthesis (Unkovskiy et al., 2018), b) implant for voiding the bladder (Hassani et al., 2017), and c) multimaterial sports mouthguard with various shore hardness (Unkovskiy et al., 2021a), d) multimaterial silicone auricular prosthesis with various shore hardness (Unkovskiy et al., 2021b).

were able to print it with shore hardness ranging from 20 A to 60 A which is the limit of DOD. The inner layer is printed with 20 A which gives optimal comfort. The outer layer needs at least 85 A for sufficient shock absorbance. Thus, for the purpose of a mouth guard, there is a need for a soft biocompatible elastomer that can be printed in multiple hardness ranging from 20 A to 90 A. The ACEO also suffers from low z resolution which is 0.4 mm. A much-improved resolution in the z-axis is also needed to eliminate the stair-case effect felt by the user.

3.2. Vat photopolymerization

Another category of 3D printing is vat photopolymerization. It utilizes light of a certain wavelength with enough energy to initiate the polymerization of a photosensitive polymer resin contained in a vat. The photosensitive resin used here has a photoinitiator that when struck by a light creates reactive species that instigate crosslinking thereby solidifying the exposed part. This photocuring process is done step-by-step until it forms the desired final part. There are a lot of variations to this branch of 3D printing, namely, Stereolithography (SLA), Digital Light Processing (DLP), Continuous Liquid Interface Production (CLIP), Two-Photon Polymerization (TPP), and Tomographic Volumetric Printing (TVP).

3.2.1. Stereolithography (SLA), Digital Light Processing (DLP)

SLA and DLP have almost the same setup where a thin layer in between the building plate and the vat is cured by light. Their processes are almost similar except on the light source. SLA uses a laser beam that scans the layer point by point while DLP uses a projector that illuminates light in 2-dimensional patterns. This makes DLP a faster process compared to SLA. DLP makes use of several moving micromirrors called Digital Micromirror Device (DMD) that direct light to the printing area. To form a pattern, DMDs point the light to the pixel area to be cured and

point elsewhere for areas not to be cured. Another variation to DLP is called Liquid Crystal Display (LCD) 3D printing wherein light is emitted using an LCD screen that shows patterns layer by layer (Quan et al., 2020).

Gonzalez et al. (2020) utilized DLP for forming complex-shaped microfluidic chips (Fig. 5b). These were of high optical transparency, flexibility, and stretchability. Moreover, because of the unreacted acrylic double bond remaining after the 3D printing process, surface functionalization by UV-induced grafting in the post-processing step is possible. This makes it more advantageous compared to the traditional manufacturing of microfluidics.

Ding et al. (2022) resorted to the use of DLP printing to fabricate elastomeric knee meniscus scaffold with optimized structure and function (Fig. 5d). The meniscus is a shock-absorbing cartilage located in between the knee joint. Its low self-healing ability makes the old age population suffer knee joint problems. FDM and DIW printing suffers from rough and even surface for fabricating meniscus that critically requires a smooth surface to avoid intense wear on the cartilage. Thus, DLP was found to be a suitable printer for this purpose. The resin is composed of polyurethane acrylate (PUA) and small molecular drug Kartogenin (KGN) necessary for meniscus repair. After printing, the scaffolds' surface underwent a modification process utilizing polydopamine (PDA) to promote cell retention and adhesion. With this, the final product had mechanical performance and spatial structure the same as the natural meniscus. This study also solved problems relating to commercially used meniscus grafts which suffer from unsatisfactory biocompatibility with stem cells and the unavailability of fine 3D structure.

DLP can also be used for printing sensors. Sandwiching an elastic dielectric film between two highly conductive layers of electronic conductors is a common method of manufacturing embedded sensors (Lind et al., 2017) (Zhou et al., 2019). During prolonged use of sensors, the

Fig. 5. Elastomeric medical devices 3D printed using vat photopolymerization: a) bioreabsorbable airway stent (Paunović et al., 2021), b) microfluidics (Gonzalez et al., 2020), c) pulmonary artery model (Loterie et al., 2018) and d) meniscus scaffold (Ding et al., 2022).

weak bonding and dissimilar mechanical strengths between layers may result in relative displacement between the electrodes and dielectrics, causing signal drifts and performance degradation. To solve this problem, Yin et al. (2019) utilized chemical bonding of components of the embedded sensor using dual-material DLP printing with the schematic as shown in Fig. 6. This was done by first using UV curing a first precursor resin which is a water-dilutable PU acrylate (WPUA). This served as the dielectric layer. After printing the intended number of layers of this, the printing is paused and the resin tank is replaced with a second precursor resin composed of an ionic conductive hydrogel (polyacrylamide/poly (ethylene glycol) diacrylate/magnesium ions), which acts as the electrode. The printing is then resumed. The acrylic groups in the two resins and their similarity in the solvent polarity allow the strong chemical bonding at the boundary of these two resins.

3.2.2. Continuous Liquid Interface Production (CLIP)

CLIP 3D printing developed by Tumbleston et al. (2015) is a DLP process where it uses an oxygen-permeable membrane window at the bottom of vat. This membrane is made of amorphous fluoropolymer (Teflon AF2400) that allows the passage of oxygen creating a thin layer

of oxygen in between the resin and the vat membrane. The oxygen layer inhibits the polymerization process forming a “dead zone” with thickness in the order of tens of micrometers that prevents the cured layer from sticking to the vat. This makes it a faster continuous process compared to DLP that needs to detach each printed layer from the vat.

The CLIP technology is employed on commercially available printers of Carbon3D Inc. Their elastomer resins are Sil 30 and EPU 40 which are proven biocompatible resins. Sil 30 is a silicone urethane elastomer that is well-suited for skin-contact applications (Xometry). It is also used for other applications such as intravaginal rings (Januszewicz et al., 2020) and soft suction for robotic gripper (Koivikko et al., 2021). EPU 40, on the other hand, is a polyurethane elastomer for high elasticity and tear resistance applications (Carbon Inc, 2021). Both Sil 30 and EPU 40 are composed of part A and part B components that are mixed in a pre-defined ratio.

3.2.3. Two-photon polymerization (TPP)

TPP is another VPP process similar to SLA except that it uses ultra-short laser pulses that cause two-photon absorption instead of single-photon. The fabrication in SLA is limited only through layer-by-layer

Fig. 6. Embedded sensor with chemical bonding of components printed with DLP: a-c) Schematic illustration of DLP printing using two resins by initial curing with a first resin and then replacing it with a second resin. d-f) Schematic of the cross-linking in the resin on the first resin (d), at the interface of the two resins (e), and on the second resin. g) Schematic of the equivalent circuit for sensing (Yin et al., 2019).

method but TPP, on the other hand, can print by laser writing throughout the volume of the transparent photosensitive resin. Among all 3D printing technologies, this has the finest resolution of 100 nm (Zhou et al., 2020). The first reported TPP printing of elastomer was in 2014 by Coenjarts et al. (Coenjarts and Ober, 2004) who printed PDMS. Using radical-initiated curing approach, they were able to achieve feature size from 0.3 to 0.6 μm . One company providing commercially available TPP printer is Nanoscribe which can print with a fine XY resolution at 400–500 nm (Nanoscribe). Several researchers have utilized this fine-resolution printer for fabricating bioinspired microstructures (Fiorello et al., 2021). Nanoscribe has its silicone-based elastomer resin, the IP-PDMS. Bunea et al. (2021) were the first to discuss the capability of this TPP technology together with this IP-PDMS resin. Due to silicone's low surface energy, Bunea et al. (2023) employed it to directly print superhydrophobic micro-hoodoo reentrant structures reaching a water static contact angle of 158°. This elastic resin has Young's modulus of 15.3 MPa, which is equivalent to human connective tissues such as ligaments and cartilage (Bunea et al., 2021).

3.2.4. Tomographic Volumetric Printing (TVP)

TVP or also known as Computed Axial Lithography (CAL) is the reverse method of computed tomography (CT). A series of radiographs from different angles are taken in CT scanning to create a 3D visualization of an object. On the other hand, TVP uses the scan of the object or the virtual 3D model to generate different amounts of energy in the form of light. The photosensitive resin is exposed from multiple angles and projections. The accumulation of a high dose of energy from various projections effectively cure the resin and shape it into the desired form of the 3D object (Kelly et al., 2019). Areas with low exposure will remain in the liquid form. This method can print at a much faster speed ($>105 \text{ mm}^3/\text{h}$) than SLA and DLP and allows printing of more viscous resins in the range 4–93 Pa s (Loterie et al., 2020) at which silicone is included. This method can achieve a resolution of 80 μm for outside dimension and 500 μm for the inside (hollow) dimension using a low-étendue illumination system (Loterie et al., 2020). Successful and fast TVP printing was done by Loterie et al. (Loterie et al., 2020), (Loterie et al., 2018) for producing centimeter-scale soft silicone artery in less than 30s (Fig. 5c).

One commercially available volumetric 3D printer with silicone as one of its compatible materials is Tomolite tomographic bioprinter by Readily3D (Readily3D). It uses low light dose that makes it cell-friendly and applicable to shape-sensitive cells and biomaterials. Its building envelope is limited to a build diameter of 12.5 mm and a height of 27 mm with print time from 20 to 120 s. Its optical resolution is 40 μm .

Another type of volumetric 3D printing is linear volumetric 3D printing which works in a principle called xolography that is developed by Regehy et al. (2020). It is the first commercially available volumetric 3D printer and is named "xube". It uses photoswitchable photoinitiators that react to two intersecting light beams of different wavelengths. This has ten times higher resolution than CAL and four to five orders of magnitude more volume throughput than TPP. The build volume for this method is limited to $30 \times 50 \times 50 \text{ mm}$ size with 15 μm and 80 μm resolution in the lateral and vertical directions, respectively. For a build volume of $10 \times 17 \times 30 \text{ mm}$, the resolution goes as fine as 5 μm in lateral direction and 40 μm in the vertical direction. Its print time typically ranges from 20 s to 5 min (xolo GmbH, 2022).

3.3. Indirect 3D printing

Another way of additive manufacturing of elastomer is called indirect 3D printing where the mold is the one 3D printed. This is then followed by the usual injection molding or casting process for silicone or polyurethane. This is usually done because of the difficulty of 3D printing an elastomer directly and the limitation of available biocompatible resins.

Comina et al. (2014) utilized 3D printing to produce the templates

for molding the PDMS on glass lab-on-a-chip. Rapid improvement in 3D printing has gone to the extent of printing nanoscale features going to 60–100 nm resolution (Limberg et al., 2022). It is through this that fabrication of lab-on-a-chip is now made possible without the need of a clean room and rigorous photolithographic processes thereby making the overall process significantly cheaper with lesser time and effort.

The ongoing development to further enhance the resolution of 3D printing also makes it popular in producing stretchable electronics (Fernandes et al., 2019). It does not only eliminate the need for stencil, mask, and clean-room lithography process, it also makes it easy to produce microstructures on components such as substrates, electrodes, and sensing elements (Liu et al., 2018). Reviews made by Fernandes et al. (2019) and Liu et al. (2018) list a summary of stretchable devices manufactured using 3D printing technologies. One example of the use of silicone elastomers with microstructures is its application as dielectric for electronic devices. In a study by Hao et al. (2020), they utilized an indirectly 3D-printed silicone dielectric elastomer with both pillar and cavity microstructures. The microporous structure formed in the elastomer is essential to achieve larger capacitance change under a pressure level. This dielectric is a part of their developed capacitive-based flexible pressure sensor that can be applied to soft robotics, electronic skins, and wearable devices.

Peng et al. (2021) conducted an investigation that used indirect 3D printing for wearable sensors. They created a 3D-printed sacrificial mold in the form of scaffolds. It was then cast with highly conductive polymer composites made of PU and carbon nanotubes. The final product is a porous flexible strain sensor that has a high stretchability of approximately 510% and outstanding recoverability. The porous structure of the sensor makes it lightweight and has higher elasticity. The patient-specific shape made it comfortable to use. When tested with human use, this sensor showed that it is capable of accurately sensing human motion, including gait analysis and finger movements, demonstrating its potential applicability for smart wearable devices.

Kamat et al. (2021) resorted to indirect 3D printing for producing micro/nano surface structures with high aspect ratios such as micropillars using soft polymers. The low tensile strength of PDMS of around 5 MPa makes it difficult to direct 3D print it. The difficulty in printing fine-resolution surface structures is also due to the long curing time and the high viscosity of PDMS. Thus, they proposed a workflow that uses a 3D-printed thin-walled sacrificial metallic mold wherein the PDMS will be cast. After casting, the metal mold was removed via acidic etching which only reacts with the metal and not with PDMS. This process, though effective, requires a lot of steps, and materials, and is time-consuming.

TPP can be used to fabricate a mold for replication of high-resolution micro/nano surface features. Liimatainen et al. (2020) utilized indirect 3D printing using TPP-printed mold to fabricate omniphobic bioinspired fibrillar adhesives made of PDMS.

Although surface roughness created in FDM printed parts is viewed as a significant drawback in direct 3D printing, Lee et al. (2021) discovered that it can be advantageous in indirect manufacturing by using an FDM printed mold to build surface patterns in PDMS polymer to get anisotropic mechanical characteristics. This molded element has been demonstrated to have potential applications in improving the movements of medical soft robots. Kang et al. (2021) used the surface patterns created by FDM printing to create molded PDMS with superhydrophobic surfaces, which are difficult to obtain using the vat photopolymerization technique. Aravind et al. (2022) created a self-moisturizing contact lens by mold casting PDMS onto an FDM and DLP 3D-printed mold. The mold has microchannels that, when repeated, facilitate water capillary flow.

In a study by Davoodi et al. (2020a), porous silicone constructs were produced using indirect 3D printing. This was done because of the difficulty of achieving submillimeter dimensions if directly 3D printed using DIW. The sacrificial molds used here to form porous constructs were made using cheap FDM 3D printers. The porous silicone construct

formed from this is biocompatible and can be used for tissue constructs.

Table 1 compiles examples of the use of 3D-printed elastomers in the medical field. It should be noted that to commercialize 3D-printed medical devices, compliance with regulatory bodies must be met. One of which is the US FDA guidance document “Technical Considerations for Additive Manufactured Medical Devices (US FDA, 2017)”. This document outlines the most important aspects of the overall 3D printing process and its testing and characterization.

4. Challenges in 3D printing of silicone and PU-based elastomers and the strategies to overcome it

Difficulties experienced in 3D printing elastomers are discussed in this section with the recent developments on how these are addressed by several researchers. There are problems though that remain unresolved due to the current limitations of the printer or the ink/resin.

4.1. FDM

4.1.1. Filament buckling

As discussed in Section 3.1.1, FDM works by feeding a filament into a heated liquefier using a pair of rollers. The melt coming out of the nozzle tip of the liquefier is deposited to form the 3D printed part. In a typical design of FDM printer, there is a gap between the rollers and the liquefier where the filament is free or unsupported. The flexible filament has the tendency to buckle in this gap as shown in Fig. 7a. This is more likely to occur when using a smaller diameter nozzle to generate finer quality prints since extruding the melt in through a smaller area needs more force. To avoid this, a critical pressure must be considered which can be derived from Euler’s buckling equation for a cylindrical beam with fixed ends:

$$\sigma_{cr} = \frac{\pi^2 E}{(L/R)^2} \quad (2)$$

where E is the material’s Young’s modulus, L is the length of the filament in between the rollers and the top of the liquefier (which is the same as the length of the gap between the rollers and liquefier), and R is the radius of the filament. In the process of melting through the length of the liquefier, there is an observed pressure drop that can be described by the following equation (Venkataraman et al., 2000) (Awasthi and Banerjee, 2021):

$$\Delta P = \frac{8\eta Ql}{\pi r^4} \quad (3)$$

where η is the viscosity, Q is the volumetric flow rate, l is the length of the liquefier, and r is the radius at the tip of the nozzle (Venkataraman et al., 2000) (Awasthi and Banerjee, 2021). Since the exit of the nozzle is nearly atmospheric pressure, it can be assumed that this ΔP is in absolute pressure and it is the same pressure on the filament before entering the liquefier.

To avoid buckling of filament in the gap between the rollers and the liquefier, the ΔP should not exceed σ_{cr} . This condition can be expressed in the following equation considering a scaling factor, k (Venkataraman et al., 2000):

$$\frac{\Delta P}{k} < \sigma_{cr} \quad (4)$$

The k , depends on the nozzle used, the volumetric flow rate, and the material (Venkataraman et al., 2000). Evaluating equations (2)–(4), we can get the following criterion to enable printing in FDM:

$$\frac{E}{\eta} > \frac{8 \eta Ql (L/R)^2}{\pi^3 r^4 k} \quad (5)$$

According to this calculation, the filament should have a larger value of E/η to prevent filament buckling. Because of their high Young’s

modulus, typical stiff thermoplastics would have little trouble attaining this. On the other hand, TPEs would struggle to achieve this due to their low Young’s modulus.

One solution suggested in a review by Awasthi et al. (Awasthi and Banerjee, 2021) to avoid TPE filament buckling is by closing the gap between the roller and the liquefier as shown in Fig. 7b using an extended guide tube. This design, however, still poses some small space between the drive wheel and the guide tube that can make a super-soft TPE buckle. Hence, a further redesign can be done with the use of a longer guide tube extending past the drive wheel and with one of the drive wheels semi-entering the guide tube with a semi-circle cut out to push the filament as can be seen in Fig. 7c (Awasthi and Banerjee, 2021).

The Flexion Extruder (Diabase Engineering, USA) is a commercially available extruder with a mechanism that is nearly identical to that of Fig. 7b. However, in this device, two guide tubes are employed, one above the rollers and one below the rollers that extends into the liquefier.

Another solution to avoid filament buckling is introduced by Leng et al. (2020) by directly feeding the nozzle with biocompatible TPU pellets, not a filament. They designed a new 3D printer called conical screw-based extrusion deposition (CSBED) system where the pellet feedstock is directly fed on a large taper conical screw that plasticizes and extrudes it. This method is also a time-efficient way of printing since the development of filaments from pellets would not be necessary anymore especially since the availability of biocompatible filaments is still limited up to now.

4.1.2. Print speed

The softness of thermoplastic elastomer would also then necessitate the need for different printing parameters compared to the typical rigid FDM filaments. The feed rate, for example, for acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) and PLA which are commonly used materials for filament, is typically in the range of 20–50 mm/s. On the other hand, for a commercially available flexible filament Ninjaflex, the optimum value was observed to be at 5 mm/s (Wang et al., 2017). This value must be lower to avoid clogging the print nozzle. If the feed rate is set too high, there will be rapid thinning out of the extruded ink which will then cause holes in the printed part (Wang et al., 2017). This required low feed rate makes it 4–10 times slower than printing using rigid polymers. The overall printing of the microfluidic system, for example, took about 5 h in the study of Wang et al. (2017). The low print speed though is seen as necessary to get a quality print (Georgopoulou et al., 2021).

4.1.3. Print quality

In using FDM to print microfluidics, the roughness of the print which is not visible for a molded PDMS makes it prone to trapping of sample materials in bead-based assays. This roughness or low resolution of FDM can be attributed to the relatively large nozzle size. The nozzle needs to be larger to compensate for the high viscosity of the melt (Michaelli and Hopmann, 2016). To alleviate this problem, Garg et al. (2022) studied the key process parameters that affect the printing accuracy of TPU. The results revealed that the layer thickness is the most important parameter to it followed by printing speed and then infill density.

Lin et al. (2021) optimized the parameters of printing TPU via FDM. High-quality prints were achieved by increasing the melt-extrusion feeding ratio and decreasing the hatch spacing gap during rastering. This led to reducing porosity further resulting in improved tensile strengths and tear resistance up to ~95% and ~126.8% of those of injection molded parts, respectively. The researchers’ next research goal is to test employing a square hole to lower the porosity of the prints and so improve their mechanical properties.

Georgopoulou et al. (2021) optimized the parameters for 3D printing several commercially available thermoplastic elastomer-based filaments of different shore hardness, the FilaFlex 70 A, FilaFlex 82 A, FilaFlex 95 A, NinjaFlex, FiberFlex 40D, Yousu 98 A, and Eel. After doing optimization to print all these filaments at the same printing parameters, it was

Table 1
Research studies on 3D printed elastomers for different biomedical applications.

AM Method	Material	Specific AM	Application	Ref.
Extrusion-based	TPE (Ninjaflex, Fenner Drives Inc.),	FDM	Microfluidics	Wang et al. (2017)
	TPE filament (eLastic, Shenzhen Esun Industrial Co., Ltd)	FDM	Diabetic foot insole	Ma et al. (2019a)
	TPU 95 A (Yisheng New Material Co., Ltd)	FDM	Bionic sports sole for the elderly	Xie et al. (2021a)
	Glycol-Modified Polyethylene Terephthalate (PETG) and Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU)	FDM	Biofunctional maxillofacial implants	Katschnig et al. (2020)
	Elastollan TPU, tetracycline hydrochloride (TC)	FDM	Anti-infective dialysis catheter	Mathew et al. (2019)
	Elastollan TPU, rifampicin	FDM	Medicated cardiovascular prosthesis	Martin et al. (2021)
	Elastollan TPU, 17- β -estradiol	FDM	Estradiol-eluting urogynecological mesh implant	Farmer et al. (2021)
	Graphene/PDMS composite	DIW	Wearable strain sensor for skin mountable electronic device	Wang et al. (2019a)
	PDMS microspheres and carbon nanotubes	DIW	Tactile sensor	Wang et al. (2019b)
	LSR Ecoflex50 and Ecoflex30 (Smooth-on Inc.)	DIW	Meniscus implant	Luis et al. (2020)
	Silicone	DIW	Personalized polymeric aortic heart valve implant	Coulter et al. (2019)
	NuSil with Vascular Endothelial Growth Factor (VEGF) microspheres	DIW	Macroencapsulation device	Levey et al. (2021)
	Material Jetting	PDMS (Sylgard 184, Dow Corning Corp)	FRE	Pulse oximeters
ACEO Silicone (Wacker)		DOD	Facial and auricular prosthesis	Unkovskiy et al. (2018) , Unkovskiy et al. (2021b)
ACEO Silicone (Wacker)		DOD	Customized sports mouthguard	Unkovskiy et al. (2021a)
TangoBlackPlus (PolyJet, Stratasys)			Implantable device for voiding the bladder	Hassani et al. (2017)
MED625FLX (PolyJet, Stratasys)			Surgical guide	Cappello et al. (2022) , Candelari et al. (2023) , Talevi et al. (2022)
Different UV and thermal cure silicones (Wacker Elastosil P7670, NuSil MED-4086, NuSil CF18-2186, BluesStar Silbione LSR 4305, Wacker Silpuran 6000/05, Wacker Elastosil LR 3003/03, Momentive Silopresn UV Electro 225-1) diluted in Dow Corning OS-2		DOD	Dielectric elastomer actuator	McCoul et al. (2017)
Pitch-based carbon fibers, dual UV/moisture curable silicone (RTV 800-400), silicone thinner		DOD	Carbon fiber/silicone composite sensor for wearable biomonitoring devices	Davoodi et al. (2020b)
Vat photopolymerization	Flexible photoresin from NingBo ZiGong Intelligent Technology Co., Ltd.	SLA	Flexible pressure sensor for electronic skin	Xia et al. (2021)
	Customized biomedical ink based on poly (D,L-lactide-co- ϵ -caprolactone)	DLP	Bioresorbable airway stent	Paunović et al. (2021)
	UV Electro 225 and UV LSR catalyst (Momentive Performance Materials)	DLP	Tissue-mimicking phantom for medical imaging	In et al. (2017)
	EGORad 2800 (TRAD), phenyl bis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (BAPO), Disperse red 1 methacrylate (DR1-MA), Methyl methacrylate (MMA)	DLP	Microfluidics	Gonzalez et al. (2020)
	EGORad 2800 (TRAD), phenyl bis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (BAPO), Disperse red 1 methacrylate (DR1-MA), Methyl methacrylate (MMA)	DLP	Microfluidics	Gonzalez et al. (2020)
	Synthesized polyurethane acrylate (PUS), reactive diluent isobornyl acrylate (IBOA), photoinitiator bis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phenyl phosphine oxide (PI 819), small molecular drug Kartogenin (KGN)	DLP	Meniscus scaffold	Ding et al. (2022)
	Hydrogel (polyacrylamide/poly (ethylene glycol) diacrylate/Magnesium ions), water-dilutable polyurethane acrylate	DLP	Sensor for wearable devices	Yin et al. (2019)
	Polyurethane elastomer (EPU40, Carbon Inc.)	CLIP	Custom shoe midsole	Zolfagharian et al. (2021)
	Custom-formulated silicone-based photoresin	TVP	Pulmonary artery model for pre-operative training	Loterie et al. (2018)

Fig. 7. Redesign of FDM printer to allow printing of soft TPE filament: a) FDM scheme with high free column length, b) FDM with guide tube extending to the wheels, c) FDM with guide tube extending above the drive wheels with a semi-circle cut out on one side of the tube for one of the drive wheels to get into direct contact with the filament (colored red) (Awasthi and Banerjee, 2021).

found that printing below 230 °C causes inadequate flow, while at a temperature above 230 °C, there was excessive stringing. Also, the printing bed temperature is found to be a critical parameter. Poor part adhesion was observed at bed temperature below 45 °C. A higher bed temperature was avoided to prevent introducing internal stresses. It was found that for a successful extrusion and flow of material, it is necessary to use an extrusion multiplier of 1.7, a value higher than most thermoplastic filaments (around 1) (Gordeev et al., 2018). Higher printing speeds than 15 mm/s result in poor print quality due to underextrusion. In conclusion, it was found that lower printing speed and higher extrusion multiplier compared to typical thermoplastics were key parameters for a satisfactory result.

Other ways to improve the print quality can be seen same as addressing mechanical anisotropy as detailed in the next section.

4.1.4. Mechanical anisotropy

The anisotropic property presents a significant challenge in FDM printing (Zohdi and Yang, 2021). Banerjee et al. (2019) conducted a study comparing the mechanical properties of thermoplastic elastomers (TPEs) printed using FDM and traditional injection molding. The study revealed that the mechanical properties of the printed TPEs were lower due to weak interfacial adhesion, leading to layer delamination. To address this issue, the researchers added carbon black as an additive to improve mechanical performance. Through experimentation, they determined that loading of 7.5 per hundred rubber (phr) of carbon black was optimal for achieving a balance between the thermoplastic elastomeric and mechanical properties of the printed TPEs.

With parameter optimization, Hohimer et al. (2017) achieved an isotropic material property of a 3D-printed TPU. This was attained using negative air gap regardless of the raster orientation and nozzle temperature. Because of the softness of TPU, this isotropy is attainable as compared to rigid thermoplastics (Hohimer et al., 2017).

Another solution to mechanical anisotropy was developed by Wang et al. (2021) by utilizing self-healing mechanism. The thermally activated self-healing property was achieved through the dynamic bonds of TPU molecular chains with dynamic urea. The internal gaps in between the filaments are intended to be healed thus improving the interlayer adhesion and its overall mechanical performance. Moreover, this self-healing property can allow the printing of simple structures and assembling these to form the intended final object thereby avoiding the use of supporting structures for overhanging features. This also speeds up the printing process for large-sized objects. The self-healing TPU also proved to have isotropic property with high mechanical property of more than 30 MPa in all directions.

Similarly, a high-quality FDM printed self-healing TPU (SH-TPU) with no visible filament layer was developed by Ritzen et al., 2021. The

material used here was synthesized using long diol oligomer (Cro-Heal™2000), diisocyanates, and diisocyanate, and 2-Ethyl-1,3-Hexanediol (EHD) chain extender. The resulting SH-TPU has soft block containing hydrogen bonds and aliphatic side branches and the hard block is composed of aromatic interactions and hydrogen bonds (Fig. 8a). The resulting print was compared to a commercially available TPU-based filament Ninjaflex. Even when printed with a larger infill distance to Ninjaflex, the synthesized self-healing TPU resulted in an isotropic part because of better interfilament fusion at both the horizontal x-y plane and vertical z direction. Even though the mechanical property of this self-healing TPU was found inferior to the Ninjaflex, the ability to completely recover from macroscopic damage proves it can last long.

4.2. DIW

4.2.1. Rheology

The viscosity of uncured silicone is low, hence DIW inks are usually added with fillers and other rheological modifiers to make it self-supporting and to provide thixotropy. To make the silicone printable, Zhou et al. (2019) added nano silica fillers as rheological modifier without compromising the elastomeric property of silicone. The final product achieved 2000% stretchability with increased mechanical property.

For the application to microfluidics, solid-state scintillators and other devices that need transparency, the addition of the needed fillers for printability is a problem in achieving the required transparency. Fumed silica, for example, has a refractive index mismatch with polysiloxane. To address this, Ford et al. (2021) developed transparent polysiloxane inks for DIW by refractive index matching of the base polysiloxane and the rheological fillers. These inks also showed thermochromic effects that pose significant use for sensing applications.

Zheng et al. (2018) developed a novel technique that enables the printing of low viscosity silicone ink by employing a thiol-ene click chemistry UV photopolymerization process for rapid resin curing, thereby facilitating self-supporting capabilities. This photopolymerization method demonstrates superior speed compared to the conventional free radical photopolymerization approach. Notably, it eliminates the need for supporting materials when printing low viscosity ink and removes the necessity for support structures in overhanging designs. An important advantage of using low viscosity ink is the ability to easily mix or change ink constituents, allowing for ink versatility and the opportunity to modify the properties of the cured materials. The process demonstrated the capability of printing silicone within the range of Shore 00 (11.0–79.0).

4.2.2. Print accuracy

The resolution of the printed fiber in DIW printing is dictated by the nozzle diameter. Most print parameters are identified using trial and error (Duoss et al., 2014). A systematic way of determining the accuracy of the diameter of the printed fiber is through creating a theoretical model and calibration as implemented by Zhou et al. (2019) when they were printing highly stretchable silicone elastomers. The diameter of the printed silicone fiber can be calculated based on the conservation of volume:

$$d = \alpha D / \sqrt{V/c} \quad (6)$$

where α is the die-swelling ratio, D is the nozzle diameter, V is the printing speed, and c is the extrusion speed. This equation can further be simplified to predict the diameter d at different printing speeds:

$$d_2 = d_1 \sqrt{\frac{V_1}{V_2}} \quad (7)$$

where d_2 is the intended fiber diameter, d_1 is the current fiber diameter,

Fig. 8. Self-healing TPU: a) Chemical structures of the components and the resulting self-healing TPU, b) Images viewed on different planes of the Ninjaflex and SH-TPU samples printed at 0.5 and 0.8 mm infill distance, respectively, c) mechanical behavior and print quality of SH-TPU and Ninjaflex (Ritzen et al., 2021).

V_1 is the printing speed obtaining d_1 , and V_2 is the changed printing speed to obtain d_2 . Using this theoretical model, printing parameters (nozzle diameter and air pressure) were optimized leading to fast printing speed of >25 mm/s while maintaining high accuracy of maximum error not exceeding 6% (Zhou et al., 2019).

4.2.3. Print speed

Liravi et al. (Liravi and Toyserkani, 2018) employed a novel approach by integrating DIW and material jetting printing to achieve rapid printing of highly viscous resins. Their method combined the advantages of material jetting and DIW techniques, harnessing the high printing precision of the DIW system and the fast-printing speed of the jetting system. The printing process involved using the DIW printhead to create the frame of each layer, while the material jetting printhead was responsible for printing the infill. As a result, they achieved a printing speed that was 10–20 times faster than traditional extrusion methods.

4.2.4. Overhanging structure

There are several studies working on finding ways on how to make overhanging structures printable. Freeform reverse embedding is one of the solutions to this as discussed in Section 3.1.3. Another solution done by Zheng et al. (2018) (discussed in Section 4.2.1) is through the use of fast curing using thiol-ene click chemistry UV photopolymerization process that allows the print to support itself quickly. Su et al. (2020), on the other hand, printed silicone elastomers with self-supporting hollow structures in the submillimeter regime by selecting inks with sufficient yield strength combined with careful consideration of the profiles or stacking orientation of the overhanging structures. With this, the as-printed silicone inks have sufficient yield strength to overcome the bending moment brought about by gravity but only within a certain

range of angle. The smallest critical angle for the RTV silicone which was used in their study is 37° from the vertical axis, above which no deformation of overhanging structures was observed. Walker et al. (2019a), on the other hand, developed a framework on 3D printing silicone without support by characterizing the rheological and curing kinetics of silicone to determine how the silicone material cures with time and temperature. The operating condition that gave an increased silicone stiffness allowed the printing of complex structures without the use of support. However, this method can only be used for printing parts with overhangs $<35^\circ$ from the vertical. Another method was done by Hamidi et al. (Hamidi and Tadesse, 2020) by using carbohydrates glasses as a sacrificial material to support the silicone printed. This allowed the printing of hollow channels.

4.2.5. Printable time of 2-component mixed silicone

Typical way of preparing silicone for DIW printing is by first mixing the two components of silicone and then storing in traditional syringes (Duoss et al., 2014) (Kolesky et al., 2016) (Lind et al., 2017). This, however, shortens the allowed printable time of silicone ink because it will start curing even at room temperature. It will also affect the rheological properties of the ink during printing. To resolve this, Zhou et al. (2019) designed a novel printer that allows printing while mixing the two-component silicones that are stored separately. This makes the extension of printing at an infinite time.

4.3. FRE

In FRE, there can be a problem of trapped uncured support within the solid infill. To address this, Greenwood et al. (2021) developed a process of curing the trapped support. They made the support curable only when

it is within the solid-infill part and not in other locations around the printed part or within the reservoir. The key to achieving this is through the addition of silicone thinner to the support matrix. This cures when mixed with silicone ink.

4.4. SLA, DLP, and CLIP

4.4.1. Adhesion to vat membrane

The light source for SLA and DLP can be positioned either at the top or bottom of the vat. The setup wherein the light source is positioned at the bottom is called bottom-up because the building platform moves from the bottom going up to build the layers of the part. The other way around is called top-down setup. Bottom-up setup is faster than the top-down approach because the resin is refilled into the printing zone easily. In the top-down setup, a wiper is needed to spread the resin evenly in the area every after printing each layer thus making the overall process slow. Also, for resins that polymerize using free radical polymerization process, the top-down setup is prone to oxygen inhibition unless it uses inert gases such as nitrogen to blanket the polymerization process from oxygen. The disadvantage of using a bottom-up setup, on the other hand, is the adhesion of the cured layer to the vat (Liravi et al., 2015).

The adhesion to the vat that causes peeling off effect per layer in a bottom-up configuration does not create much trouble for 3D printing rigid parts but is a concern when using soft and elastomeric materials. The weak intermolecular forces between layers of a soft elastomer will cause significant deformation of the part and it may become more evident when printing thin walls. Worse, it can lead to printing failure caused by the detachment of the cured layer to the previous layer when the build plate moves away from the vat. One approach to prevent printing failure due to the weak bonding between layers is by increasing the dynamic intermolecular interactions in the silicone resin through incorporation of thiourea groups as was done by Du et al. (2021). A simpler approach can be over-curing the layer to increase the bonding force with the previously cured layer. This, however, will lead to a poor surface finish and oversized dimensions (Zhou et al., 2013). Another solution is to use high layer thickness (Zhao et al., 2019) to reduce the number of detachment instances but this will compromise the z-resolution of the part even when the printer can go at a finer resolution. A commonly used method to address this issue is by using low surface energy fluorinated ethylene propylene (FEP) film or Teflon sheet (Bhattacharjee et al., 2018), (Rodriguez et al., 2021) or silicone coating for non-silicone photorezin (Zhou et al., 2013). Yet, even with this, the adhesion force is still observed to be high (Zhou et al., 2013) (He et al., 2018). This is also prone to scratches and therefore needs regular replacement. On the other hand, the CLIP technology does not suffer adhesion problems with its oxygen inhibition layer forming the “dead

zone”.

Thrasher et al. (2017) tackled this problem by using an immiscible denser liquid at the bottom of the polymerizable resin as illustrated in Fig. 9a. This immiscible brine liquid does not mix with the photorezin at the top, thus preventing the adhesion of the polymerized part to the vat. This idea is based on a patented solution by Carbon3D (Robeson et al., 2015).

An improved version of using immiscible liquid was developed by Walker et al. (2019b). Instead of a stagnant liquid, they used a mobile liquid interface, which is clear fluorinated oil, to both solve adhesion problems and cool the print avoiding thermal deformation. This is believed to print 100 times (Zastrow, 2020) faster than the CLIP technology (Tumbleston et al., 2015). Because of the high-speed printing, there is high energy dissipation observed from the polymerization reaction that is highly exothermic. Hence, the movement of the clear liquid helps in removing heat. This further avoids thermal deformation of the print and unwanted clouding of the resin which can affect the X–Y resolution printing. With this technology, they were able to print butadiene rubber structure at a rate of 30 $\mu\text{m/s}$ with a resolution of 100 μm .

Another approach is developed by De Beer et al. (2019) who utilized dual-wavelength volumetric photopolymerization confinement with the setup as can be seen in Fig. 9b. Two sources of light of different wavelengths are used to simultaneously do photoinitiation and photoinhibition to a meth (acrylate) resin. The combination of these two sources of light causes an inhibition volume just above the window. Above this volume, there is a photopolymerization reaction. This approach results in rapid continuous printing with a speed of approximately 2 m/h. Also, by varying the intensity of the light source per pixel, surface topographical patterning can be achieved in a single exposure without the need for z-translation (De Beer et al., 2019).

4.4.2. Overhanging structure

There is also a need to make a support for overhanging structures for vat photopolymerization. Since so far, these vat photopolymerization technologies only use one material for printing (not multi-material), then the support structure for an elastomer printing would still be made of a low-stiffness material that can easily collapse or deform. There would be a need to use a greater amount of support material. It then poses a challenge on how to remove this soft structure from the main part. This process can cause damage to the main part such as small cracks that can eventually easily propagate. Hence, Danny Kim et al. (2016) proposed a new method called hydrostatic 3D printing (H3P) that utilizes hydrostatic pressure to support the part during printing as illustrated in Fig. 10a. This process uses low one-photon polymerization (LOPP) to cure the part spot-by-spot and continuously in the liquid resin. The LOPP structures were found feasible but with low repeatability. This

Fig. 9. Vat photopolymerization setup to solve adhesion problems to the vat: a) use of biphasic wherein a denser liquid sits at the bottom of the active photorezin (Thrasher et al., 2017), and b) use of dual wavelength for photoinitiation and photoinhibition (De Beer et al., 2019).

Fig. 10. Setups to print highly viscous resin: a) use of hydrostatic force for stabilization of formed part (Danny Kim et al., 2016), b) rotating vat (Rodriguez et al., 2021), c) vat photopolymerization with temperature-controlled building plate and vat (Paunović et al., 2021), d) hybrid DIW and vat photopolymerization 3D printing (Rau et al., 2021).

process requires that the polymer has the same density before and after curing to avoid creating motion due to a change of density. The concept of H3P is still in the infancy stage and but there is research to further understand this dead zone behavior due to LOPP (Danny Kim et al., 2019).

4.4.3. Rheology

Another important consideration for effective printability of the resin is that it must have good fluidity. The polymerization process will only proceed through the capability of the resin to go through photocrosslinking activity. Additionally, the resin must have low viscosity to ensure that it will evenly spread into the print area during the layer-by-layer printing. This will also facilitate faster recoat of the building area thus speeding up the printing process. Likewise, the reactive components will interact at a rapid rate also causing faster curing. The use of low viscosity resin also enhances the resolution of the printed part (Bao et al., 2022). It also facilitates easy detachment of the cured layer from the vat membrane (Bao et al., 2022). This is important because high adhesive force will cause delamination of printed layers. However, one of the greatest challenges for SLA or DLP printing of an elastomer is meeting the recommended viscosity of the resin which is ideally less than 5 Pa s (Taormina et al., 2018). Because of the required low viscosity, inks are restricted to using low molecular weight chains. This produces rigid and brittle parts. For an elastomer to be flexible and have high mechanical properties, the molecular weight of the oligomer should ideally be high. However, this high molecular weight oligomer in resin creates high viscosity. Silicone, for example, has a viscosity >5 Pa s (Loterie et al., 2018). Fillers are also needed to enhance the toughness of an elastomer, but it also causes an increase in viscosity (Zhao et al., 2019).

Research nowadays is then moving towards enabling high-viscosity printing. An example of which is by using a rotating vat which rotates every after printing a layer to present a new area with uncured resin after (Rodriguez et al., 2021) as illustrated in Fig. 10b. This setup eliminates the need for the resin to completely recoat the printing area in the vat. Similar setup was used by Zhao et al. (2019) when they printed their developed highly viscous superstretchable silicone elastomer resin. Their resin formulation has viscosity of the resin reaching 20,610 cp

(20.610 Pa s) which is beyond the recommended 5 Pa s max viscosity for DLP printing. Hence, the use of a rotating vat was needed.

Paunović et al. (2021) used temperature-controlled vat and building plate to reduce the viscosity of their ink in producing bioresorbable elastomer stent. This is shown in Fig. 10c. Printing at 70–90 °C resulted in an effective decrease in the viscosity of the photopolymers without triggering thermocuring. At the temperature of 80 °C, they were able to successfully print a customized bioresorbable elastomer stent that has mechanical properties comparable to state-of-the-art silicone stents.

Without increasing the viscosity of the resin to attain elastomeric properties, Du et al. (2021) were able to increase the intermolecular interaction in silicone resin while maintaining the softness and stretchability of the part. This was done by developing a novel photocurable PDMS-based resin incorporated with thiourea segments which increases intermolecular interactions between polymer chains through hydrogen bonding. It did not increase the viscosity of the part because the H-bonded thiourea arrays are geometrically nonlinear. This then prevents crystallization and makes the resin maintain its low viscosity at an amorphous state.

The use of solvent can also be an option to reduce the viscosity of the resin. However, this may lead to shrinkage after evaporation (Du et al., 2021). Another solution can be by adding a reactive diluent (liquid monomer with low viscosity) to the formulation to decrease the viscosity of the resin (Li et al., 2019). For the case of printing biodegradable elastomer, the reactive diluent can alter the structure of the cross-linked network and the cross-linking density which may result in reducing the elastomer's biodegradability. Hence, Sandmeier et al. (2021) used a well-defined macrophotoinitiator to create a solvent- and reactive diluent-free biodegradable elastomer resin. High-quality 3D printing of biodegradable elastomer was obtained by covalently connecting the photoinitiator to the polymer chain with structural similarity to the macromomers.

Another solution is done by Rau et al. (2021) who combined the capability of DIW to print high-viscosity resin with the high-resolution printing capability of vat photopolymerization as illustrated in Fig. 10d. In this way, UV-curable elastomer resins such as urethane acrylate elastomer photoresin can have high viscosity that can cure with high tensile strength and toughness (Rau et al., 2021).

4.5. TPP

Though TPP has a high resolution, the printing process is very slow, and the print dimension is usually small which makes it impractical to be used in mass scale production. The build volume of Nanoscribe printer is only limited to $100 \times 100 \times 8$ mm. A 25 (magnification) $\times/0.80$ (numerical aperture) microscope objective has only 400 μm diameter maximum effective writing field (Bunea et al., 2021). For structures larger than this, stitching of multiple print areas is needed. This stitching process then creates artefacts in between the two print areas. This slightly deteriorates the quality of the print. Thus, the optimal quality of the print is limited by the maximum effective writing field of the microscope objective.

4.6. Volumetric 3D printing

Printing of a highly viscous photosensitive resin of elastomers is challenging in SLA or DLP. This is where TVP comes in handy as the printer only allows the use of highly viscous resin. High viscosity is required so that the cured part will not undergo sedimentation during printing (Loterie et al., 2018). This makes TVP a suitable printer for viscous silicone or elastomer resin. The downside of using TVP is that its resin is limited to only those that have high viscosity, high reactivity, low absorption, are transparent, and do not scatter light (Sampson et al., 2021). Transparency is needed so that light patterns will be able to illuminate through the whole diameter of the build volume. The photoinitiator concentration can be adjusted to make the optical attenuation length (l) longer than the width of the printed part in the following equation:

$$c = \frac{1}{\alpha l} \quad (8)$$

where α is the absorption coefficient of the photoinitiator for a particular wavelength (Loterie et al., 2018). This equation then implies that a low photoinitiator concentration is needed to print large objects. It will, however, lead to poor polymer conversion and low mechanical properties. This then limits the printer to only print small-sized objects (Loterie et al., 2018).

4.7. Indirect additive manufacturing

PDMS Sylgard 184 is widely utilized in microfluidics for soft lithography applications (Johnston et al., 2014). The curing process of this silicone involves a hydrosilylation mechanism, wherein the Pt-based catalyst cross-links with vinyl-terminated oligomers. However, when PDMS Sylgard 184 is cast into a 3D-printed mold, the curing process becomes inhibited. This phenomenon can be attributed to the release of various chemicals from the 3D-printed mold, including polyethylene glycols, diethyl-phthalates, unreacted monomers, and phosphineoxide photoinitiators, all of which hinder the catalyst's effectiveness (Venzac et al., 2021). Hence, Venzac et al. (2021) investigated 16 commercially available resins and identified the required post-curing treatments (UV and thermal treatments) needed to replicate the 3D printed mold. Results indicated that phosphine oxide-based photo-initiators are poisoning the Pt-based PDMS catalyst as they leak out of the 3D-printed devices. However, photo-initiators were both removed and recombined into high molecular weight species that were sequestered in the molds after being exposed to UV and/or thermal treatments.

5. Elastomer photoresins/filaments for biomedical application

With the growing interest of the medical device industry to soft elastomeric polymers, several companies are into producing photocurable resins for 3D printing technology. Examples of these are listed in Table 2 which is partly adapted from a review by Guttridge et al. (2022).

Some of these photoresins are elastomer-like resins that have a lower elongation at break compared to the real elastomer. It will therefore be more prone to tear damage. It should be noted that a direct comparison of the material properties cannot be directly done using Table 2 because of the different standards at which these values were obtained. It is recommended to check these on the supplier's website. Among the commercially available resins, the resins that showed superior elongation at break are TrueSil (Spectroplast, 2022) from Spectroplast. Unfortunately, these are not for sale because the company is a printing service company that prints the model on their premises. A photoresin with a shape memory effect is commercially available. This is the Luxaprint flex resin that is a clear biocompatible medical device class IIa resin and is specifically made to be used for soft, massive earmoulds. It has shape memory effect that allows it to return to its original shape after being deformed (DETX GmbH Co, 2021).

Even though commercial resins for vat photopolymerization are convenient to have, there is a lack of a full knowledge on the formulation of these resins. This information is kept confidential by the supplier due to proprietary reasons. Although there is research (Palaganas et al., 2017) tuning the properties of commercially available resins, the confidentiality of the resin formulations in general limits researchers to play around with properties such as stiffness. The composition of the resin is also critically needed to easily confirm its biocompatibility. Also, it limits users to only use the printers provided or recommended by the ink suppliers. These constraints then led researchers to formulate their own resins with some of it listed in Table 3.

Recent progress in formulating novel ink is already comparable to a commercial PDMS such as Sylgard-184 (Dow) which has a Young's modulus of 1.3 MPa and 140% elongation at break (Bhattacharjee et al., 2018). Some of these formulations are superstretchable that it even surpassed Sylgard 184's elongation at break (Zhao et al., 2019) (Du et al., 2021). Zhao et al. (2019) developed a highly viscous superstretchable silicone elastomer resin. The final product of this can elongate up to 1400%, a value higher than reported photocured 3D printed elastomers and commercially available thermally cured silicone elastomers. They used thiol-ene click reaction between a synthesized branched mercaptan-functionalized polysiloxane and different molecular weight vinyl-terminated PDMS. The use of high molecular weight vinyl-terminated PDMS proved to create elastomer with low hardness and high elongation at break compared to low molecular weight. Silica particles were also added to the resin formulation to enhance the mechanical property of the elastomer. It is because of these silica particles that the elongation at break of the elastomer has reached up to 1400%. Du et al. (2021) was able to develop a photoresin forming a silicone with 100% elongation at break with excellent compressive elasticity. This was achieved by increasing the dynamic intermolecular interactions in the silicone resin through the incorporation of thiourea groups. The mechanical property of this custom-formulated silicone photoresin can be tuned by adding "oligomeric" and "polymeric" PDMS segments in the macromonomers and controlling hydrogen bonding ratio from this. Silicone photoresins is also developed for low-temperature application as was done by Serrine et al. (2019). They developed the vat photopolymerization photoresins using two different fully amorphous PDMS terpolymers, containing either diphenylsiloxy or diethylsiloxy repeating units that showed elastic performance to temperatures as low as -120 °C by suppressing crystallization. On another study, Serrine et al. (2018) demonstrated that PDMS-based photoresin that reacts to thiol-ene coupling and free radical polymerization was feasible. It simultaneously undergoes linear chain extension and crosslinking. Results show that this dual chain reaction provides printed objects with twice as much elongation at break than just a free radical reaction alone.

There are also silicone and TPU-based developed inks that has self-healing properties (Liu et al., 2020) (Li et al., 2019) (Yu et al., 2019). Liu et al. (2020) developed a silicone photoresin that is not just self-healing but also reprocessable making this an eco-friendly material. This formulation undergoes thiol-ene reaction between thiol and

Table 2
Commercially available 3D printer filament and resins for elastomer and elastomer-like polymers for biomedical application.

Photoresin	Manufacturer/ Provider	AM technique	Shore Hardness	Young's modulus [MPa]	Elongation at break [%]	Color	Biocompatibility	Manufacturer intended use/ Application investigated in research
NinjaFlex	NinjaTek	FDM	85 A	26	660	Various	ISO 10993-5 (Wang et al., 2017)	Insoles, helmet inserts, organ model printing for teaching, braces for joints, prosthetics, orthotics, grip pads, vibration dampening, shock absorption, gasket, seals, guards, soft robotics Microfluidics (Nelson et al., 2019)
SainSmart Clear Flexible TPU	SainSmart	FDM	95 A	–	–	Clear	Cytotoxicity test (Nelson et al., 2019)	
ChronoSil (polycarbonate-based silicone elastomer)	AdvanSource Biomaterials	FDM	75 A-75D	6.9 ± 0.85	–	–	ISO 10993-5 (Bachtiar et al., 2020), USP Class VI	
Elastollan 80 A	BASF	FDM	80 A	–	–	–	ISO 10993-5, –4 (Martin et al., 2021) (M'Bengue et al., 2023)	–
Figure 4 Rubber-BLK 10	3D Systems	DLP	59D, 97 A	540	80	Black	ISO 10993-5, –10 or USP Class VI	For parts with slow-rebound for touch applications such as grips, handles and bumpers, as well as strain-relief applications, couplings, over molds, etc.
Figure 4 Rubber-65a BLK	3D Systems	DLP	65 A	23	126	Black	ISO10993-5, –10	For grips, handles, gaskets, bumpers, seals, vibration dampening components
BioFlex MF ULWA A70	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	70 A	<400	>80	Clear	Stated to be non-cytotoxic, no certification found	Ideal for bioprinting flexible applications and ultra safe biocompatible flexible systems
BioFlex MF A70	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	70 A	<400	>80	Clear		
BioFlex MF ULWA A60	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	60 A	<300	>90	Clear		
BioFlex MF A60	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	60 A	<300	>90	Clear		
BioFlex MF ULWA A50	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	50 A	<10	>90	Clear		
BioFlex MF A50	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	50 A	<10	>90	Clear		
BioFlex MF ULWA A20	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	20 A	<2	>100	Clear		
BioFlex MF A20	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	20 A	<2	>100	Clear		
Bioflex MF ULWA A10	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	10 A	<1	>100	Clear		
Bioflex MF A10	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	10 A	<1	>100	Clear		
Bioflex A20 MB ULWA	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	20 A	<2	>100	Clear		
Bioflex A20 MB	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	20 A	<2	>100	Clear		
Bioflex A10 MB ULWA	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	10 A	<1	>100	Clear		
Bioflex A10 MB	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	10 A	<1	>100	Clear		
EPU 40	Carbon	CLIP	72 A (instant), 71 A (5 s)	8	400	Black	ISO 10993-5, –10	For high elasticity and tear resistance applications
EPU 41 Green	Carbon	CLIP	72 A (instant), 71 A (5 s)	6	250	Green	ISO 10993-5, –10	For elastomeric lattices where high resiliency is needed
Sil30	Carbon	CLIP	35 A (Instant), 31 A (5 s)	3	350	Grey	ISO 10993-5, –10	Skin contact applications (e.g. MyFit Solutions earbud tips)
LuxaPrint Flex	Detax	DLP, SLA	>90 A at room temp., >70 A at body temp.	not specified	>60	Clear	ISO 10993-1	Shape memory resin (DETAX GmbH Co, 2021) intended for swim plugs, hearing protection, earmoulds, in-ear-monitoring Hearing aid applications
E-Shell 500	EnvisionTec	DLP	87 A	not specified	60	Clear	ISO 10993 Class IIa	
IBT	FormLabs	SLA	<90 A	>16	>25	Clear	ISO10993-5, –10, ISO 7405	Indirect bonding trays
IP-PDMS	Nanoscribe	TPP	not specified	15.3	240	not specified	ISO 10993-5, USP 87	Soft, flexible, and elastic 3D microstructures

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Photoresin	Manufacturer/ Provider	AM technique	Shore Hardness	Young's modulus [MPa]	Elongation at break [%]	Color	Biocompatibility	Manufacturer intended use/ Application investigated in research
Otoplastic 3Dresyn OTO-S (Version S)	3Dresyns	SLA, DLP, LCD	90 A	<500	<35	Clear, red, etc	Not specified	Durable soft ear shells and tips and other otoplastics, hearing aids, and medical devices
MED625FLX	Stratasys	Material Jetting (Polyjet)	73–77 A	not specified	45–55	Clear	ISO 10993-5, -10, -11, -18, -17, -3, and USP Class VI	Flexible medical devices requiring 30+ days skin contact, 24-h mucosal contact
TrueSil A20	Spectroplast	DLP, SLA	20 A	not specified	1000	Clear, and various colors	ISO 10993-5, -10	Healthcare applications (e.g. prosthetics, audiology products, wearables, etc), industrial and technical applications (e.g. sealing elements, dampers, gaskets, etc), micro parts
TrueSil A35	Spectroplast	DLP, SLA	35 A	not specified	650		ISO 10993-5, -10	
TrueSil A50	Spectroplast	DLP, SLA	50 A	not specified	530		ISO 10993-5, -10	
TrueSil A60	Spectroplast	DLP, SLA	60 A	not specified	360		ISO 10993-5, -10	

vinyl-functionalized polysiloxanes to make it UV printable. It also goes through thermal curing between carboxyl and amido functionalized polysiloxanes. Because of the reversible breakage and reformation of ionic bonds formed between the carboxyl and amido functionalized polysiloxanes, it gained self-healing efficiency of 97% and repeated reprocessability with 90% recovery of its virgin mechanical strength. Li et al. (2019) formulated 3D-printable self-healing polyurethane acrylate elastomers containing disulfide bonds. The resulting product has a tensile strength of 3.39 MPa and elongation at break of 400%. It can recover 95% of its original shape after healing at 80 °C for 12 h. This performance makes it suitable to be used in flexible electronics.

Commercially available biocompatible filaments and inks for FDM and material jetting are limited. So far, the commercially available filaments that are proven biocompatible in various studies are Ninjaflex (Wang et al., 2017) and Elastollan (Martin et al., 2021). To produce more biocompatible flexible filaments, a simple extrusion from a commercially available medical-grade TPU can be done (Xiao and Gao, 2017). Filaments can be custom-made to suit a specific application as was done by Haryńska et al. (2018) who developed their own formulation for a medical-grade TPU filament. For material jetting, McCoull et al. (2017) were able to make commercially available UV and thermal cure silicone elastomers to be printable in a DOD inkjet printer by diluting these in Dow Corning® OS-2 solvent. From this, they printed dielectric membranes as thin as 2 µm.

5.1. Biocompatibility

A biocompatible material is defined as a substance that can interact with biological systems and perform its intended use without eliciting an unacceptable degree of unwanted effects on living tissues (Mozafari, 2020) (Guttridge et al., 2022). The material's biocompatibility cannot be assessed based solely on the knowledge of the chemical network of the composition of the bulk material. A variety of material properties influence the host reaction depending on the intended application and thus further influencing its biocompatibility. This includes micro- and nanostructure, morphology, porosity, degradation profile, degradation by-products, wear debris release profile, surface energy, surface chemical composition, and surface topography, to name a few (Mozafari, 2020). The actual mechanism of biocompatibility on the material's interface between tissues is still unclear (Mozafari, 2020). A systematic way of analyzing the biocompatibility of a material is by following standard methods by International Standards Organization (ISO) and/or by the U.S. Pharmacopeial Convention. Biocompatibility is commonly assessed using ISO 10993 (ISO, 2020). In the US, USP Class VI is implemented to evaluate the biocompatibility of plastic materials (Guttridge et al., 2022). Tables 2 and 3 detail the biocompatibility tests in commercially available resins and custom-formulated resins, respectively.

Depending on the application, purely using a PU or silicone may not be enough for an implant to be biocompatible as it needs to satisfy its intended use. Silicone, for example, has been reported to introduce bronchial inflammation when used as a respiratory stent (Puma et al., 2000). Such adverse immune reactions can lead to major problems with the healing process around the implant. Thus, Barthes et al. (2021) added an immunomodulatory coating to a DIW-printed silicone to limit excessive inflammation after implantation. The in vivo investigations on male Wistar rats revealed that just 33% of those with bare silicone implants survived, but 100% of those with coated silicone implants did. In the case of a knee implant, Ding et al. (2022) used a DLP-printed PU bionic meniscal implant (Fig. 11) with its resin infused with a small molecular drug and functionally modified the implant's surface with polydopamine (PDA) to improve biocompatibility and hydrophilicity, which is beneficial for cell retention and adhesion. The in vivo study on rabbits showed that this drug-infused and surface-functionalized PU meniscus implant has better cartilage protection and good tissue regeneration compared to just a pure PU implant.

Surface roughness has been shown to affect implant biocompatibility. It is a well-known issue with silicone breast implants that resulted in the global recall of Allergan's BIOCELL textured breast implant because implants with higher surface roughness are associated with a higher risk of breast implant-associated anaplastic large cell lymphoma (BIA-ALCL) (Doloff et al., 2021). Surface roughness is a notoriously inherent artifact, particularly in extrusion-based 3D printing. A study then investigating the effect of surface roughness on the biocompatibility of the implants was done by Zühlke et al. (2021) using a DIW-printed silicone implant. The tissue reactivity was examined in vivo by implantation of the DIW-printed silicone under the skin in the paravertebral of mice. Although the printing increased the sample's surface roughness, it had no effect on cytotoxicity and tissue reactivity after two weeks of observation.

The mechanism of photopolymerization used (free radical, cationic, or thiol-ene polymerization) can also have an impact on biocompatibility. The conversion rates of free radical reactions utilizing meth (acrylate)-based resins are modest, ranging from 60 to 90% (Oesterreicher et al., 2016). When unreacted monomer or oligomer leaks into the human body, it can trigger allergic and cytotoxic reactions (Oskui et al., 2016). This, therefore, necessitates extensive post-processing of printed parts (Xu et al., 2021). Furthermore, meth (acrylate)-based complexes are susceptible to hydrolytic degradation, which can result in the generation of meth (acrylic) acid, which can lower the local pH and pose adverse effects on the surrounding tissue. (Bagheri and Jin, 2019). The cationic reaction of epoxidized polysiloxane has a slower reaction rate than the free-radical system, and the photoinitiator photoproduct has potential causticity and biotoxicity (Xiang et al., 2019). Thiol-ene reaction, being a type of click chemistry, occurs at a fast rate with high efficiency, is insensitive to oxygen or water, and is shown to have

Table 3
Photocurable elastomer and elastomer-like resin compositions made by researchers.

Material	AM Process	Photoresin formulation	Shore Hardness	Young's modulus [MPa]	Elongation at break [%]	Exposure time (s)	Layer height used (μm)	Biocompatibility test	Intended application	Ref.
Silicone	DLP	(methacryloxypropyl)methylsiloxane]-dimethylsiloxane copolymer Ethyl (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phenyl phosphinate (TPO-L) Orasol orange	Not specified	11.45 \pm 2.20	–	12	100	Not specified	PDMS membrane for gas-liquid-contacting; microfluidic chip application	Femmer et al. (2014)
	DLP	methacryloxypropyl terminated polydimethylsiloxane (methacryloxypropyl)methylsiloxane]-dimethylsiloxane copolymer Ethyl (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phenyl phosphinate (TPO-L) 2-isopropyl thioxanthone (ITX)	Not specified	0.52–0.94	140	1.5	50	Cytotoxicity	Cytocompatible microfluidic systems with elastomer actuators	Bhattacharjee et al. (2018)
	SLA	synthesized Poly (mercaptopropylmethylsiloxane-co-dimethylsiloxane) (PDMSSH) 2,4,6-Trimethylbenzoyldiphenyl phosphine oxide (TPO) α , ω -vinyl terminated polydimethylsiloxane 2-hydroxy-2-methylpropiophenone (Darocur 1173)	Not specified	0.2 MPa Tensile strength	158	–	50	In vitro cytotoxicity, in vivo test on mice	Wound dressing, customized soft tissue scaffolds	Xiang et al. (2019)
	SLA	Vinyl terminated polydimethylsiloxanes (mercaptopropyl)methylsiloxane-dimethylsiloxane copolymers (MFS-1, -2) amphorous hexamethyldisilazane treated fumed silica Isopropylthioxanthone (ITX) (Type II radical initiator) 4-methoxyphenyl (MEHQ) 2-ethylhexyl 4-(dimethylamino)benzoate (EHDA) 2-(2Hbenzotriazol-2-yl)-4,6-di-tert-pentylphenol (BTA) (photo-absorber)	12 A–54 A	0.20–1.58	140–243	5–10	50	Not specified	Gaskets, soft robotic components	Rodríguez et al. (2021)
	SLA	Thiol-modified silicone oil (KF-2001) Amino-modified silicone oil (KFT-306 A) TPO-L	–	~0.175–0.225 MPa (UTS)	340–400	Minimum ~15s to get ~90% conversion, ~30s for 100% conversion	–	Not specified	Stated to have a potential for durable wearable and flexible electronic devices	Liu et al. (2020)
	DLP	Vinyl-terminated polysiloxane (RH-Vi304) carboxyl-modified silicone oil X-22–3701 E (PDMSDMAA) toluene Irgacure 819	23 A \pm 2 A	0.58 MPa (UTS)	51 \pm 6	24	100	Not specified	Pneumatic gripper; prototyping applications on simulated human tissues, stimuli-responsive materials, wearable devices, and soft robotics	Thrasher et al. (2017)
	DLP	Vinyl-terminated poly (dimethylsiloxane) Synthesized Poly ((mercaptopropyl)methylsiloxane) 2-Hydroxy-2-methyl-phenyl-propane-1-one (PI 1173) phenyl bis (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (PI 819) Fumed silica, precipitated silica	~15 A	2.59 MPa (UTS)	1400	–	100	Not specified	Stretchable electronics	Zhao et al. (2019)

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Material	AM Process	Photoresin formulation	Shore Hardness	Young's modulus [MPa]	Elongation at break [%]	Exposure time (s)	Layer height used (μm)	Biocompatibility test	Intended application	Ref.
	DLP	synthesized Methacrylate-Terminated PDMS (Polymeric)–PDMS (Oligomeric)–Thiourea GENOMER 1122 3-[Tris (trimethylsiloxy)silyl]propyl methacrylate Irgacure 819, TPO-L, and Irgacure 1173	–	–	1000	20	75	Cytotoxicity	Stated to have a potential for medical devices, wearable devices, soft robotics	Du et al. (2021)
	TVP	Vinyl-terminated PDMS Fumed silica reinforced vinyl-terminated (Mercaptopropyl)Methylsiloxane-dimethylsiloxane TPO-L	–	0.28	88	–	N/A	Not specified	Surgical model of soft organs	Loterie et al. (2018)
PU-based	DLP	Synthesized polyurethane acrylate containing disulfide bond hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA) 2-Hydroxy-2-methyl-phenyl-propane-1-one (PI 1173) phenyl bis (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (PI 819)	–	3.39 MPa (UTS)	400	10	200	Not specified	Stated to have a potential for flexible electronics, soft robotics, and sensors	Li et al. (2019)
	DLP	Ebecryl 8413 (Allnex) cyclic trimethylpropane formal acrylate (Ebecryl CTFA, Allnex) Diphenyl (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (TPO, Allnex)	75.2 A–85 A	10	~170	–	100	Not specified	Stated to have potential for soft actuators, soft robots, and flexible electronics	Pooput et al. (2020)
	DLP	Ebecryl 8413 (Allnex) 2-(((butylamino) carbonyl)oxy) ethyl acrylate (Genomer*1122, Rahn) Diphenyl (2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phosphine oxide (TPO, Allnex)	29.8 A–36.6 A	~2	365	–	100	Not specified	Stated to have potential for soft actuators, soft robots, and flexible electronics	Pooput et al. (2020)
	DLP	Synthesized polyurethane acrylate (PUS), reactive diluent isobornyl acrylate (IBOA), photoinitiator bis(2,4,6-trimethylbenzoyl) phenyl phosphine oxide (PI 819), small molecular drug Kartogenin (KGN)	–	21.2 MPa Tensile strength, 80.3 MPa tensile modulus	331.2	3	100	In vivo study in healthy rabbits	Meniscus scaffold implant	Ding et al. (2022)
	DLP	Different synthesized polyurethane acrylate oligomers: poly- (tetrahydrofuran) acrylate (PTMGA), poly (propylene glycol) acrylate (PPGA), polycaprolactone diol acrylate (PCLA) Isobornyl acrylate (IBOA) 2,4,6-trimethyl benzoyl diphenyl phosphine oxide (TPO) 2,5- bis(5-tert-butyl-2-benzoxazolyl)thiophene (BBOT)	PPTMGA: 48 \pm 0.5 A PPPGA: 45 \pm 0.7 A PPCLA: 83 \pm 0.4 A	PPTMGA: 6.7 \pm 0.7 PPPGA: 6.9 \pm 0.3 PPCLA: 70.2 \pm 1.3	PPTMGA: 414.3 \pm 7.6 PPPGA: 227.6 \pm 11.1 PPCLA: 327.6 \pm 8.9	13	100	Not specified	Wearable stretchable electronic sensor for body motion monitoring	Peng et al. (2020)
Others	DLP	poly (DLLA-co-CL) methacrylate Sudan I phenylbis (2,4,6-trimethyl-benzoyl)phosphine oxide (BAPO)	–	3–6	>60	3.3	–	In vitro cytocompatibility (ISO 10993–5, –12), In vitro degradation, In vivo study in healthy rabbits	Bioresorbable airway stent	Paunović et al. (2021)
	DLP	2-hydroxyethyl acrylate (HEA) Butyl acrylate PDMSDMAA Irgacure 819	22 A \pm 1 A	1.01 MPa (UTS)	338 \pm 8	15	100	Not specified	Pneumatic gripper; prototyping applications on simulated human tissues, stimuli-responsive	Thrasher et al. (2017)

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Table 3 (continued)

Material	AM Process	Photoresin formulation	Shore Hardness	Young's modulus [MPa]	Elongation at break [%]	Exposure time (s)	Layer height used (µm)	Biocompatibility test	Intended application	Ref.
									materials, wearable devices, and soft robotics	
		cetrimonium bromide								

lower cytotoxicity than (meth)acrylate-based resin (Oesterreicher et al., 2016), (Xi et al., 2014), (Lee et al., 2014), (Hoyle et al., 2010). As a result, Xiang et al. (2019) employed thiol-ene photopolymerization between vinyl and thiol-functionalized polysiloxanes (Fig. 12a) to 3D print silicone elastomer using an SLA printer. In vitro experiments on human prostate cancer cells revealed that the samples were noncytotoxic. Samples were implanted as a wound dressing on mice, and it showed that wound healing occurred in nearly 95% of the sample group but just 56% of the control group (Fig. 12b). The samples also displayed antibacterial activity, as they inhibited the development of Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative (*E. coli*) bacteria.

The photoinitiator utilized also has an impact on biocompatibility in a photopolymerized product as an unreacted residual photoinitiator can produce cytotoxicity if the photoinitiator utilized is not biocompatible (Wang et al., 2022), (Trudel and Massia, 2002). Photoinitiators for biomedical applications must be highly water soluble, non-cytotoxic, and compatible with visible low-power light sources (Tomal and Ortyl, 2020). However, there are only a limited number of commercially available biocompatible photoinitiators (Tomal and Ortyl, 2020). A list of these biocompatible photoinitiators can be found in the review by Tomal and Ortyl (2020).

Care should be highly considered when integrating particles into silicone or TPU inks. Silicone inks for DIW needed particles or fillers such as silica to modify the rheological properties of the ink to make it printable (Zhou et al., 2020). However, if the sizes of these particles are not controlled and include nano-sizes, then it can raise health concerns (Huang et al., 2022). Even though these nanoparticles are within the elastomer matrix, it must be proven that they do not migrate out of the printed object into the environment. In the cases where liquid-metals are used for soft-electronics, studies on numerous research have shown that liquid metals do not impart significant toxicity when attached to the skin or injected into the body in a small amount although there is a need to verify this in the long-term biocompatibility for wearable devices (Park et al., 2021). Encapsulating all these materials should be studied for safety.

The biodegradability of the 3D printed object, particularly as an implant, is extremely important. The following section compiles studies on biodegradation and its effect on the biocompatibility of various 3D printed elastomer materials.

5.2. Biodegradation

Biodegradation is important for implants intended for temporary healing since it eliminates the need for a second surgery to remove it. There are biodegradable elastomers that can be used as an alternative to inert silicone. One of these is developed by Paunović et al. (2021) who made customized bioresorbable airway stents (Fig. 12b) with elastomeric properties. This was produced using DLP and customized resin composed of dual-polymer photoinks based on poly (D,L-lactide-co-ε-caprolactone)s [poly (DLLA-co-CL)s]. The resin is made up of a mix of high and low molecular weight poly (DLLA-co-CL) methacrylates (Fig. 13a). This resulted in increased strength from the high cross-linking density and improved elasticity from the long and flexible polymer chains. Its mechanical performance was found to be comparable to that of medical silicone materials used to make airway stents. The stent, which was manufactured from an optimum dual-polymer resin with a 75/25 wt ratio of high and low-Mw poly (DLLA-co-CL), was mechanically stable and stayed in place in vivo in a healthy rabbit for 7 weeks until becoming radiographically invisible. After 10 weeks, it was no longer found in the respiratory stream (Fig. 13c). In a separate in vitro study by the researchers (Paunović et al., 2022), it was observed that by adjusting the weight ratio of the low and high-Mw of the photopolymers, tunable degradation can be achieved.

The in vitro degradation of TPU blended with PLA was studied by Abdul Samat et al. (2021) for fabricating FDM filaments for tracheal scaffold implant. These two polymers, in different weight ratio, were

Fig. 11. Preparation and biological performance assessment of PU meniscal scaffold implant: (a) Synthesis of polyurethane acrylate (PUA) and mixing it with other components to form the photosensitive resin. (b) Optimization of the design using finite element analysis. (c) DLP printing of PU scaffolds (d) After printing, the surface of the scaffolds is modified with polydopamine. The final product is tested through in vitro and in vivo tests (Ding et al., 2022).

Fig. 12. Thiol-ene photopolymerization of silicone for wound dressing: a) Schematic reaction of vinyl-terminated PDMS (PDMS-Vi) and thiol-functionalized polysiloxane (PDMS-SH), b) result of wound dressing of the sample after 12 days of implantation and its comparison with the control group with no implantation (Xiang et al., 2019).

Fig. 13. Bioreabsorbable elastomeric stent: a) Schematic for the printing from resin composed of two poly (DLLA-co-CL) methacrylates with high (P1) and low (P2) molecular weights, b) 3D printed airway stent for the rabbit c) Radiographs of a rabbit during the observation period. The red line indicates the position of the stent, and the black arrows point to the C4 vertebrae (Paunović et al., 2021).

mixed by melt-compounding. The blended samples were found not miscible, but they were considered to have good compatibility because of the hydrogen bonding between the molecules of the blend with the schematic shown in Scheme 3. In vitro degradation study was done by soaking the samples in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) solution to simulate the hydrolytic degradation activity of TPU/PLA blends. The PBS solution was refreshed every 7 days for 7 months. All the samples demonstrated a gradual loss with higher concentrations of TPU exhibiting a faster degradation rate. The pure TPU and PLA samples showed a degradation rate of around 6 and 2%, respectively, in this period of 7 months. The materials' biodegradation is primarily dependent on the hydrolytic degradation of polymeric chains. Crystallinity and chain orientation of polymers are critical in degradation processes. TPU's amorphous section was more vulnerable to assault due to its loose packing than PLA's semicrystalline region. The degradation then begins with water diffusion into the amorphous structure of the TPU and is subsequently followed by random hydrolytic scission of the ester linkages. Then, the hydrolytic attack continues to the crystalline structures by also starting to break the ester bonds. In a separate test, the samples proved to be biocompatible after conducting in vitro test by checking the viability of cell culture for 3 days. In another study by the authors (Abdul Samat et al., 2023), in vivo tests were conducted. Cells grew similarly to the control group and were unaffected by degradation products or a drop in the pH environment caused by degradation.

Another study assessing the biodegradability of PLA-based TPU was done by He et al. (2022). The PLA-based TPUs were synthesized by first

Scheme 3. Schematic illustration of hydrogen bonding between PLA and TPU (Abdul Samat et al., 2021) (Feng and Ye, 2011).

doing prepolymerization which involves reacting the $-OH$ groups with the $-NCO$ groups of dicyclohexylmethane-4,4'-diisocyanate (HMDI). This is then followed by chain extension using 1,4-butanediol (BDO) as chain extender. The synthesis is shown in Fig. 14a. This FDM printable PLA-TPU formulation demonstrated shape-memory properties (Fig. 14b). In vitro cytotoxicity test showed that PLA-TPUs have no effect on L929 cells. Blood compatibility tests were also conducted, and it showed that the samples have no effect on the internal/external coagulation system. Degradation of samples by immersion on PBS was done and it revealed a minor decline in the quality of the samples during the first 46 days, after which the loss in quality became more pronounced. Only around half of the initial bulk remained after 113 days. The degradation of TPU also started with the hydrolysis of the ester group. The hydrolysate contains acidic carboxyl groups (COOH) which may speed up the hydrolysis of the polymer segments of PU. Carbamate groups can be hydrolyzed during immersion resulting in forming alcohol, an amine, and carbon dioxide, but they do so at a far slower rate than ester groups. The degradation reaction by hydrolysis is shown in Fig. 14c. Its shape memory property, biocompatibility, blood compatibility, and biodegradation properties make it potentially applicable as an intelligent biodegradable scaffold in vivo. However, the effect of degradation on biocompatibility was not assessed in this study.

FDM-printed TPU (Epaline 390 A Series) was characterized by Harýnska et al. (2020) to see its potential for cancellous bone tissue structures. It passed ISO 10993-5 cytotoxicity test. In vitro tests involving long- and short-term degradation and bioactivity using simulated body fluid incubation showed that TPU printed samples exhibit degradability suitable for long-term tissue engineering constructs.

5.3. Durability

Biodurability is defined as the ability of the material to have minimal effect on its functional properties from the host in a specific situation (Paunović et al., 2022). Silicone has been proven to be biodurable on a long-term implantation of a silicone gel breast implant which was found still intact after 32 years with no evidence of chemical biodegradation (Brandon et al., 2003). However, biodurability of 3D printed silicone has not been studied so far. On the other hand, as discussed in Section 5.2,

Fig. 14. Biodegradable PLA-based TPU: a) Synthesis of PLA-TPU, b) Shape-memory effect of PLA-TPU, c) Schematic of degradation (He et al., 2022).

TPU degrades by hydrolytic activity. To make it biostable, silicone can be added to it. This was investigated by [Bachtiar et al. \(2020\)](#) who used polycarbonate-based urethane silicone (PCU-Sil) elastomer. The samples were printed using FDM and proved to be biocompatible as per ISO 10993-5 test. The samples did not exhibit hydrolytic degradation as evidenced by no significant difference in the samples' mechanical properties. The addition of silicone could have also improved PCU's oxidative stability.

The thermal stability of silicone can also be important when it is assembled with electrical wires. Silicone's durability was seen in a study by [Hassani et al. \(2017\)](#) in their implant with shape memory alloy (SMA) actuators for voiding the bladder. The implant is composed of a 3D printed (material jetting) vest with SMA wires that contract when applied with a voltage. Longer stimulation caused overheating damaging the wires and their contraction properties. Despite this, the 3D-printed silicone did not degrade.

It is also necessary to determine the durability of the elastomers when undergoing sterilization procedures. A study evaluating the impact of gamma sterilization on the medical grade TPU (Elastollan) printed using FDM was conducted by [M'Bengue et al. \(2023\)](#). After gamma sterilization, the macroscopic color changes to yellow on the FDM samples which is a consequence of oxidation of TPU. The radiation with oxygen generated free radicals that initiated the conversion of bis phenyl methylene groups into allenes groups with conjugated double bonds. Inspection of surface properties revealed changes in the surface chemistry after sterilization. Results also showed an increase in molecular weight by 8% indicating that formation of bonds by radical recombination may have occurred. This, though, did not result in a change in the tensile properties of the samples. After sterilization, the cytotoxicity and hemocompatibility tests showed vitality of cells and no hemolytic activity which indicates its applicability for use as blood-contacting implants. Additionally, it demonstrated to be non-cytotoxic and with cell viability high above 70% after irradiation.

The durability of TPU with shore hardness 95 A printed using FDM and Stratasys' MED625FLX biocompatible resin which is compatible with their PolyJet printer are explored by various researchers as materials for surgical guides for different surgical procedures. [Talevi et al. \(2022\)](#) examined the possibility of using these materials in 3D printing a patient-specific surgical guidance tool for epicardial ablation in Brugada syndrome, a disorder associated with ventricular arrhythmias and abrupt cardiac death. For these materials to be acceptable as a surgical guide, they should withstand the sterilization process. The material's resistance to sterilization by vapor peroxide was then examined for different thicknesses of the surgical guide. TPU95A did not show any damage while two out of the 4 thickness values set for MED625FLX

showed damage after the sterilization process, but the researchers accounted for this damage to the geometry of the surgical guide rather than the parts' thickness and the material. [Candelari et al. \(2023\)](#) tested the feasibility of using TPU95A and MED625FLX materials as a surgical guide for cryosurgery that involves freezing the targeted tissue. The response of the material to cryoenergy delivery was examined on two different thicknesses of the material, 1.0 and 2.5 mm. TPU95A of both thickness and MED625FLX of 2.5 mm thickness were the ones found suitable for cryoablation treatment while the guide with MED625FLX 1.0 mm was not able to retain its shape thereby losing its function. [Cappello et al. \(2022\)](#) also tested 1.0 and 2.5 mm TPU95A and MED625FLX materials as cardiac surgical guides for radiofrequency ablation (RFA) treatment for bipolar and unipolar catheters. This treatment involves the use of radiofrequency at a critical temperature above 50 °C to destroy the heart tissue which causes arrhythmias. Results revealed that none of these materials were suitable for unipolar RFA due to thermal concerns. Moreover, only MED625FLX of 2.5 mm thickness passed thermal and geometrical stability after bipolar RFA. This then limits the surgical guide to a minimum of 2.5 mm, preventing a thinner and more flexible design. This necessitates further optimization of the clinical workflow to allow the use of thinner models.

6. Discussion

Additive manufacturing is an effective tool in the healthcare industry not just for fast prototyping but also allows the fabrication of patient-specific medical devices and implants that optimally serve users' needs. Recent advancements include innovation in multimaterial printing for applications such as personalized and customized drug delivery and sensor, complex porous structure for variable mechanical properties, continuous development of novel biocompatible filaments and resins with enhanced properties, and improvement of mechanical designs of 3D printers.

The unique properties of elastomers make them difficult to print compared to rigid polymers and thus require different ways of printing them. Recent developments discussed in this review include the strategies to overcome many challenges in printing elastomers as summarized in [Table 4](#). FDM 3D printer suffers from low speed, low resolution, filament buckling, mechanical anisotropy, and low surface finish. Effective strategies to overcome this were discussed except for low printhead speed. Due to filament buckling, the mechanical design of the FDM printer that is suitable for rigid thermoplastics needs to be redesigned to be applicable to thermoplastic elastomers. While the extrusion-based method may already be enough for devices that do not require high resolution and good surface finish such as the foot insoles that are

Table 4
Summary of the challenges of 3D printing elastomers.

3D Printing Technique	Challenges/Limitations to Printing Elastomers	Solutions	Drawbacks/Concerns
FDM	Filament buckling	Extruder design with short or no free-column length between the roller and the liquefier (Awasthi and Banerjee, 2021) Feeding the nozzle directly with pellets using a conical screw that plasticizes and extrudes it (Leng et al., 2020)	Major redesign of existing printers is needed to incorporate this solution.
	Print speed	None	Slow print speed compared to typical thermoplastics is found necessary to get quality prints (Georgopoulou et al., 2021)
	Print quality	Parameter optimization (Garg et al., 2022) (Lin et al., 2021) (Georgopoulou et al., 2021)	
DIW	Mechanical anisotropy from weak interfacial adhesion	Adding carbon black to improve the mechanical performance of printed TPE (Banerjee et al., 2019) Parameter optimization using negative air gap (Hohimer et al., 2017) Improving the interlayer adhesion by using custom filament with self-healing property (Wang et al., 2021)	Custom filament needed
	Rheology	Adding rheological modifiers/fillers (e.g. nanosilica) to silicone ink (Zhou et al., 2019) Custom silicone ink curing by thiol-ene reaction (Zheng et al., 2018)	Nanoparticles can pose health risks (Huang et al., 2022) Custom resin needed
	Printing accuracy	Parameter optimization (Zhou et al., 2019)	
FRE	Print speed	Combining DIW with material jetting (Liravi and Toyserkani, 2018)	Complex system needing two different printhead systems
	Overhanging structures	Use of freeform reverse embedding (FRE) Use of thiol-ene reaction (Zheng et al., 2018) Parameter optimization considering curing kinetics (Walker et al., 2019a) Use of carbohydrate glass (water-soluble) sacrificial support (Hamidi and Tadesse, 2020)	Limited commercially available FRE printer Custom resin needed This has been demonstrated to be only capable of printing pieces with overhangs <35° from the vertical (Walker et al., 2019a) Complex system needing two printheads with a different extruding mechanism
	Trapped uncured support within the solid infill	Use of silicone thinner that cures when mixed with silicone (Greenwood et al., 2021)	
SLA/DLP	High viscosity resin	Customized temperature-controlled printing platform to heat the resin tray (hot lithography) (Paunović et al., 2021) (Bao et al., 2022) Use of rotating vat (Rodriguez et al., 2021) Volumetric 3D printing (Bao et al., 2022) (Loterie et al., 2018) Use of solvents (Du et al., 2021) Use of reactive diluents into the resin (Du et al., 2021) (Peng et al., 2020)	Costly redesign of the printer from a commercial one Transparent resin is necessary; limited to small print size; limited commercially available printer This can cause shrinkage of the part after printing (Du et al., 2021) This can cause unwanted effects on biodegradable printed parts
FRE	Adhesion of cured elastomer to the vat	Use of biphasic printing wherein a brine is placed at the top of the vat to separate the immiscible layer from the bottom surface (Thrasher et al., 2017) Use of PTFE-lined vat or FEP/Teflon membrane (Bhattacharjee et al., 2018) (Rodriguez et al., 2021) Incorporation of thiourea segments into PDMS polymers (Du et al., 2021) Dual wavelength volumetric photopolymerization confinement (De Beer et al., 2019) Use of mobile liquid interface (Walker et al., 2019b)	Removing the brine from the resin after printing could be difficult This does not completely remove the adhesion problem. This is susceptible to damage and needs to be replaced from time to time. Custom resin is needed Custom resin is needed that reacts with dual wavelength
	Need for support due to low moduli of elastomers	Use of Continuous Liquid Interface Production (CLIP) utilizing oxygen inhibition layer (Tumbleston et al., 2015) Freeform 3D printing (Hinton et al., 2016) Use of hydrostatic force for stabilization of part during printing (Danny Kim et al., 2016) Volumetric 3D printing (Bao et al., 2022) (Loterie et al., 2018)	Removing the omniphobic fluorinated oil from the resin after printing could be difficult This mechanism does not work with thiol-ene photopolymerization. The custom resins that showed advanced properties (high elongation, and shape-memory properties) are synthesized using thiol-ene photopolymerization. Studies also show that thiol-ene could be more biocompatible compared to free radical systems. There is limited commercially available FRE printer. This technology is not yet fully developed.
	Limited photoresins	Custom formulation of photoresins	Transparent resin is necessary; limited to small print size; limited commercially available printer The curing time of elastomer resins is found to be longer compared to typical photoresins for rigid parts. The commercialization of these custom resins with improved functionality and biocompatibility could enable wide use of 3D printing elastomers for medical device applications More costly compared to direct printing
		Indirect 3D printing (Kamat et al., 2021)	

popularly printed using FDM, there is still a need to improve other 3D printing technologies for a higher quality medical device requiring higher resolution and material integrity. Vat photopolymerization demonstrates the highest resolution among the different types of printers. In addition, the vat photopolymerization types that were discussed in this review DLP, CLIP, and CAL have faster printing speeds

compared to material jetting and material extrusion (Zhou et al., 2020). However, SLA and DLP, which are the most used vat photopolymerization printers (Grand View Research), are met with several challenges. Resolving these challenges will require more studies on the mechanical modification of the vat photopolymerization printers or resin formulation. Consequently, these solutions could then be adopted

by 3D printer manufacturers and modified their printers so that it is commercially available and accessible to medical device manufacturers. CLIP is one of the commercially available printers that addresses adhesion to the vat membrane but not entirely. Parts with large cross-sectional areas will still experience capillary forces in the gap between the vat membrane and the building platform and this will potentially still induce stresses to the part. Additionally, thiol-ene reaction which is a faster reaction than free radical polymerization does not work with the CLIP mechanism. The most ideal vat photopolymerization printing for highly viscous elastomers is volumetric 3D printing. However, the build size of volumetric 3D printers is restricted to small sizes to enable light to pass through. Indirect 3D printing is also a good way of addressing all these issues related to direct 3D printing, but it does not improve the manufacturing speed in comparison to the traditional injection molding or casting methods.

There are also seen challenges in the filaments and photoresins of elastomers. It shows that the speed of depositing or curing of elastomers compared to rigid polymers is slower. The deposition of TPU needs to be slow to avoid nozzle clogging. In the case of photopolymers, it can be noticed in Table 3 that the majority of the exposure times are in several seconds which is slower compared to the typical acrylate-based photoresins that can be cured at millisecond exposure time. There are also problems in making the emerging novel photopolymers accessible. The custom-developed resins that showed self-healing, superstretchable, and reprocessable properties even for silicone require tedious and time-consuming wet laboratory work and expensive chemicals. Unless these formulations are mass-produced or commercialized at a low price, it will be hard to transfer this from the laboratory to the industrial scale.

Biocompatibility is a crucial requirement for medical devices. Although many 3D printable materials are commercially available, their biocompatibility is often assessed only according to ISO 10993-5 and -10 standards, which are sufficient for qualifying them for use in medical devices intended for contact with intact skin (long term contact) and mucosal membrane (≤ 24 h limited time contact duration) (ISO, 2020). Materials that pass ISO 10993-5 indicate the absence of toxicity harmful to living cells, making them suitable for applications involving microfluidic systems used in the study of living cells (Beckwith et al., 2018). However, only a limited number of custom-formulated elastomer photoresins have undergone biocompatibility testing. Some of these materials have been tested in vitro for cytotoxicity with cells and in vivo for applications such as wound dressing, meniscus scaffold implants, and bioresorbable stents. These studies demonstrate that 3D-printed silicone possesses biostability, while 3D-printed PU elastomers exhibit safe biodegradability. Consequently, these materials are deemed suitable for use both inside and outside the human body. It is important to note that while these 3D printed silicones/PU have demonstrated biocompatibility in various in vivo experiments on different parts of the human body, the inks used in these studies differ. Therefore, it is not possible to generalize the safe usage of silicone/PU in different areas, as material purity and composition also play significant roles in determining biocompatibility (Curtis and Steichen, 2020). It is also crucial to highlight that the biocompatibility of a 3D printing material approved for one application cannot automatically be assumed for another application within the human body (Rogers et al., 2021).

Achieving biocompatibility in filaments and inks for FDM (Fused Deposition Modeling) and DIW (Direct Ink Writing) can be readily accomplished by employing medical-grade silicone/TPU materials that have already demonstrated successful outcomes in biocompatibility tests. However, it is crucial to acknowledge that surface roughness plays a significant role in determining both the overall biocompatibility and functionality of the printed device. Therefore, careful consideration must be given to the intended function of the printed devices to ensure that surface roughness does not compromise the biological system with which it comes into contact. The selection of appropriate printing technology generating a certain surface roughness is critical to prevent adverse effects on the biological system. In such cases, the use of high-

resolution vat photopolymerization printers can be considered.

In the case of printers utilizing photopolymers, simply relying on resin labels claiming biocompatibility based on specific ISO tests is insufficient. To guarantee biocompatibility, extensive post-processing procedures (curing and cleaning) should be implemented to ensure the complete removal of any residual uncured monomers or excess photoinitiators. This step is necessary to eliminate any potential cytotoxic effects that may arise from the presence of these residual chemicals. Furthermore, when customizing photoresins to improve their properties beyond what is commercially available, various factors such as the type of photoreaction and photoinitiator used should be considered, as these have been shown to influence the biocompatibility of the resulting printed parts, though more research is needed to confirm their significant effect on biocompatibility.

7. Conclusion

Additive manufacturing has gained innovative use in fabricating elastomer medical devices. This review serves as a guide in 3D printing silicones and polyurethane elastomers for medical applications, covering issues of manufacturability, resin availability and custom formulation, and safety (biocompatibility and (bio)durability). Different 3D printing technologies discussed were initially designed to print rigid polymers. The use of elastomers then challenges the original design of these printers because of the change in viscosity, thixotropy, and stiffness of the ink. These challenges necessitated solutions that required altering either one or both the printer's mechanical design and the resin's polymer chemistry. Rheology was tweaked to make elastomer filament or resin applicable to the different printing mechanisms. In cases where original rheology is kept, the printer mechanism is the one redesigned to be able to print the highly viscous elastomer resin. However, some of these solutions have disadvantages or limitations that prevent them to be widely implemented. What differentiates elastomer printing from typical rigid polymers is its slow printing time. There is a relatively low printhead speed in extrusion-based printing and a long curing time for photoresins in vat photopolymerization and material jetting. Moreover, the printing of elastomeric medical devices is greatly hampered by the availability of cheap biocompatible elastomer resins. To enable efficient mass customization and rapid production of advanced complex elastomeric medical devices through 3D printing, it is crucial to make commercially accessible the high-performance elastomer resins that are custom formulated in different studies. Additionally, it is also essential to address the challenges associated with the printability of elastomers in various 3D printing technologies using cost-effective solutions minimizing the need for extensive modifications to existing printers.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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